

National Teachers College
Graduate Program, School of Teacher Education

**ENHANCEMENT OF CIVIC LITERACY THROUGH DISTANCE LEARNING
MODALITY: BASIS FOR CREATING A TRANSACTIONAL DISTANCE LEARNING
MODEL IN UNDERSTANDING CULTURE SOCIETY AND POLITICS**

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CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

The outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic brought many changes and challenges to people. Physical contact and communication of people have become limited unlike before the pandemic. Consequently, as the pandemic became worse, people were not allowed to have large gatherings and were very cautious with face-to-face interactions because the government put the country on lockdown to control the spread of the virus. These restrictions were imposed not only in the country but also internationally to survive each stage of the crisis (Iglesias-Sanchez et al., 2021). In light of the current situation, social media have become the “new normal” media for connection and communication. People in different fields adapted and relied on the advancement of technology because it is one of the easiest ways to adjust to the new situation that the country is facing. Also, it helps them to connect and to continue working toward their goals. All sectors have been affected by the government restrictions on face-to-face interaction, one of those is the Department of Education (DepEd), which is the basic education department of the Philippines. To continue their goals and functions, they had decided to conform to the sudden change in the learning environment from traditional face-to-face learning to online and blended learning. The Department of Education issued an order on Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in light of the Covid-19 public health emergency (DO No.012, s. 2020) . In the said mandate, DepEd had introduced the following: Flexible Learning Options (FLO), Alternative Delivery Modes (ADMs), Alternative Delivery Modules or Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) and Learning Resources (LRs) where the students and teachers could continue education without

compromising their health. The learning modalities conceptualized by the institution had become the basis of other local schools for the implementation of classes under the new normal. Hence, the University of Makati, a locally funded university of the local government of Makati, adapted the modular and online learning setup from DepEd. The university has been known since it was selected by the government specifically the Higher School ng UMak (HSU) Department to pilot test the Senior High School program in the year 2012. The school is the pioneer of senior high school that produced more than three thousand Grade 12 graduates, the first and largest senior high school graduates during the school year 2012-2013 (Rappler, 2014).

One of the core subjects under the senior high school program is Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP). Following the DepEd K to 12 Curriculum for Senior High School, the UCSP subject comprises the concepts from the three social sciences namely, Anthropology, Sociology, and Political Science. The integration of the concepts from the three fields aims to develop the student's awareness of cultural, social, political dynamics, and sensitivity to cultural diversity. These also help students to understand how culture, human agency, society, and politics work and engage students in examining the country's current human development goals. Specifically, the integration of the aforesaid concepts in the subject UCSP aims to enhance the civic literacy of the students through the inculcation of human cultures, human agency, society, politics, cultural relativism, social inclusiveness, prejudices, social and cultural competence, communities, networks, and institutions. Civic literacy provides knowledge and skills to participate effectively in civic life by knowing how to stay informed, understand governmental processes, and knowing how to exercise the rights and obligations of citizenship in local, state, national, and even global levels (Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2009, as cited in Morgan, 2016). Individuals also have an understanding of the local and global implications of civic

decisions. Hence, UCSP comprises the competencies of civic education that are required to be taught by the UCSP teachers to enhance the students' civic literacy. So, by taking up the subject, it is expected that the students must enhance their civic literacy and improve their knowledge in understanding the cultural, social, and political aspects of our society and acquire skills in participating in a democratic society. Hence, the implied purpose of the course is the enhancement of the students' civic literacy. From the scope of civic education and civic literacy, it is evident that these two have broad aspects to examine and contemplate specifically in the political, social, economic, cultural, educational, and religious concepts.

Before the pandemic, the learning modality that was implemented at the University of Makati was the actual face-to-face classroom discussion. Teachers and students had to regularly meet in the classroom two to three times a week which allowed them to have more interactions. During that period, the teaching of the UCSP subject to students involved more actual observation and interaction with the social, cultural, and political issues in society. They even had the means to conduct outreach programs outside the campus as part of their performance task. However, the abrupt changes in the learning modalities due to the pandemic changed the way UCSP has been taught. The implementation of learning activities and performance tasks in UCSP before the pandemic was more engaging since outreach programs and other community engagements were still possible. However, these activities were not possible during the pandemic because of the restrictions and classes should be done online.

Meanwhile, the high school department (Higher School ng UMak) of the university had specifically devised the modular and online learning setup with synchronous and asynchronous modalities to teach the UCSP course. These learning modalities aimed to make basic education equally available for all students regardless of their economic status. Certainly, the implementation

of distance learning with the aforementioned modalities became an alternative way to teach students and to ensure the acquisition of the learning competencies required in different subjects including Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP). However, teaching the course in an online modality has become challenging from the fact that enhancing the civic literacy of students could be more successful if they could be exposed to actual community engagements. During the online modality, UCSP activities become limited affecting the student's learning experiences and acquisition of civic literacy. Due to this type of modality, the present study aimed to utilize the Transactional Distance Learning modality by Moore and determine if this modality would enhance the civic literacy of grade 12 students in the UCSP subject. Lastly, it will propose a transactional distance learning model to enhance the civic literacy of students.

In addition, students should enhance their civic literacy to know their basic rights and obligations as citizens of the country and to actively participate in society. The UCSP subject has learning competencies that lead the students to attain and enhance civic literacy which is one of the necessary skills in the 21st century. The civic literacy that the students will acquire in the subject UCSP could serve as their foundation as they participate in civic life. However, the present distance learning modality adds more challenges to teaching the subject given the fact that it has lesser interaction than the face-to-face modality. Also, Morgan (2016) stated that some of the youths today are not ready and don't have much concern about citizenship and civic learning challenges so it could be challenging for teachers to inculcate civic literacy in students and to make students appreciate it because some of the students nowadays have less concern about citizenship. Consequently, this study aimed to design a transactional distance learning model to help enhance the learning experiences and civic literacy of students in UCSP subjects.

Background of the Study

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, all educational institutions were doing face-to-face learning modalities in educating students. Teachers and students at that time had real-time sharing of conversations. Now, real-time conversations only happen during synchronous classes in the current learning modality through online platforms (e.g. Google Meet); it enables the students to understand and immediately raise questions about the lessons taught by the teacher online. Even before the pandemic, Philippine education was already exposed to educational breakthroughs, specifically the integration of technology and innovative teaching methodologies in the classroom. For instance, in 2009 and 2006, the Department of Education created an Internet-Based Education Program (DO no. 169, S. 2009) and Open High School Program (DO 46, S. 2006). The program aims to make distance learning possible for high school students who want to study at their own pace even without attending a traditional classroom. The implementation of the distance learning program back then enabled us to identify the distance learning advantages and disadvantages. According to DepEd, the distance learning program implemented in 2009 had advantages, the program was described as flexible, time-saving, cheaper, and self-paced; however, it provided minimal social interaction, little support, problem in accessibility, and requires self-motivation. Hence, there are lots of aspects and challenges to consider when implementing distance learning.

With the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, the country's basic education institutions, headed by the DepEd, had instantly shifted from traditional face-to-face learning to distance learning modalities. DepEd offered a blended learning approach which has the following options for the students: taking lessons through online classes, modular or printed materials, television, and radio (Abad, 2020) to make education accessible to everyone even in times of pandemic. In addition, DepEd issued a memorandum on their policy guidelines for the provision of learning

resources in the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan, based on D.O. 018 s. 2020, the following strategies will be implemented: (a) Flexible Learning Options (FLO) which contains menu of learning interventions and pathways that are responsive to the needs, context, circumstances, and diversity of learners, (b) Alternative Delivery Modes (ADMs) an instructional learning modalities that do not strictly follow the typical set-up for regular classroom instruction, but follow the K to 12 curriculum in content, Alternative Delivery Modules or Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) this is a self-contained, self-instructional, self-paced, and interactive learning resources for public schools intended for learning specific topics or lesson where the learner interacts actively with the instructional material rather than reading the materials passively, and Learning Resources (LRs) it is an any text-based (print or non-print) or non-text based material (devices, tools, equipment, manipulative toys) aligned with K to 12 curriculum and as primary bases or supplements to teaching and learning processes. Consequently, no educational institutions were prepared for the sudden changes in the learning modalities but they had to handle the critical and enormous tasks to maintain quality education in the Philippines while protecting its stakeholders' health in the process (Llego, 2021). Another factor that contributed to the challenges in the implementation of distance learning is the country's low investment in Information and Communication Technology (ICT). According to 2020 Huawei's Global Connectivity Index, the Philippines has ranked 59th out of 79 countries that are categorized by the institution. The country has been classified as a "starter" when it comes to ICT investment and ICT maturity. Aside from that, the Philippines ranked fourth lowest in internet speed among the 10-member Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). This is based on the report of the Speed test Global Index (2021) from the ASEAN Information Center, which means that the quality of the internet

connection in the country is slower than the other Southeast Asian countries and this may affect the quality of the implementation of the online synchronous classes.

Furthermore, the urgent shifting of traditional face-to-face classes to distance learning did not hinder the opening of classes for the academic year 2020-2021. By that time, DepEd had to implement alternative ways to continue education despite the face-to-face restrictions by offering lessons through online classes, modular or printed materials, television, and radio. In light of the DepEd online distance learning, DepEd made a move to increase the capability of public schools by introducing various platforms that could be used in the implementation of distance learning. One of the helpful educational platforms that DepEd initiated was the so-called DepEd Commons. This is an online educational platform for public school teachers that could be reached free of data charges by all mobile data subscribers. It contains modular, television, and radio-based instructions which support educational institutions to pursue distance learning (De Leon, 2020). Asserted by Llego (2021), the DepEd Commons is convenient to the teachers and students in a way that it has fast dissemination of educational resources in different places. He also said that through the platform, interaction and remote activities are possible. Thus, platforms like DepEd commons are vital in the distance learning modality setup.

The University of Makati, Higher School of UMak (HSU, High School Department) had also implemented a distance learning setup specifically the synchronous and asynchronous distance learning modalities. The university also developed a Learning Management System, the Technology-Based Learning Hub (TBL Hub) which became the official learning platform of the University of Makati to sustain education amidst the pandemic. The TBL Hub is considered a digital learning environment that enables test submissions, discussions, announcements, and lesson banks, or in other words, it manages the learning and teaching efforts of the school. Since

the start of distance learning in the Academic Year 2020-2021, HSU has been using TBL Hub, Google Meet, and Zoom for synchronous and asynchronous classes. The learning modules were also uploaded to the TBL Hub so that the students could view and download them anytime. The University of Makati, specifically the HSU department has survived the whole academic year with the aforementioned distance learning modalities and platforms, it is evident that the educational institutions are still committed to providing quality education through the utilization of these modalities.

Despite the efforts of the Department of Education and other educational institutions, the immediate utilization of distance learning in the country resulted in challenges faced by the education stakeholders, especially students and teachers because they were the ones who were directly affected by the implementation and drawbacks of distance learning modality. Both the teacher and student have been trying to adjust to the distance learning modality. Problems were emerging in the implementation of synchronous modalities such as lack of gadgets and insufficient knowledge of technology. However, teachers have been working on their technological skills, specifically those who are not technology savvy through the series of training and webinars provided by DepEd and other educational institutions. Those training and webinars were certainly helpful since the majority of teachers had average computer competency and had no training in online teaching (Moralista & Oducado, 2020). Also, motivating students to engage in online class activities and submission of outputs is part of the challenges in distance learning. In some cases, online education resulted in more academic dishonesty, impersonal, and lack of feeling compared to face-to-face classes. All in all, the unanticipated implementation of distance learning was associated with challenges, particularly difficulties encountered by students and teachers with their internet connectivity, inadequate technological skills, and the challenges in the teaching-learning

process in the distance learning modality. Thus, the aforementioned drawbacks manifest the necessity of further support and development in the implementation of distance learning.

The University of Makati has opened its classes under the senior high school program in the academic year 2021-2022 through distance learning. One of the subjects offered in the school year 2021- 2022 was Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP). The subject has a purpose of imparting civic literacy to the students for them to know their basic rights and obligations as citizens of the country and for them to actively participate in society. However, there was a big challenge, the subject was taught through distance learning modalities (synchronous & asynchronous), which probably limited the community engagements, knowledge, and skills of students about civic education. One of the reasons was that they could not go outside to conduct community extensions or observations, their ideas on the political, cultural, and social aspects of our society could only be based on what they could watch, hear, or read on the television, radio, social media platforms, and distance learning platforms. Hence, the observation and engagement of the actual society could be difficult in distance learning. Another thing that could affect the civic literacy of students is the lack of or limited socialization with other people, which somehow hinders them from actually observing the cultural differences of the individuals in the society. In general, teaching and learning UCSP subjects could be challenging in the distance learning modalities since this subject needs authentic social engagements and observation to understand society and its culture. However, with the use of transactional distance learning modality, the students' learning engagement in the online class may be increased. Since the students could not be exposed to actual community engagements, increasing the students' engagements in class discussion could empower their civic literacy in a way that could lead them to self-realization and deepen their understanding of the social, political, and cultural contexts of the society.

In the new normal education set-up, distance learning seemed to be the only way to provide education to avoid academic freeze and its negative repercussions in education. Following the concept of Michael Moore's theory (Keegan, 1997) the present study developed a transactional distance learning model that could help improve the teaching approach in distance education that would serve as treatment and could enhance the students' civic literacy in the UCSP subject. The model was anchored on Moore's constructs of dialogue, structure, and autonomy and served as an approach to the teaching of the UCSP subject. The teaching approach that was tested in the study was reflected in the lesson plans and learning modules. This ensured that the teaching strategies and activities included in teaching the subject had sufficient dialogue and structure and could encourage students' learning autonomy. Thus, after applying the transactional distance learning approach, its effectiveness in enhancing the civic literacy of students through distance learning was determined through tests that based on Bloom's taxonomy with questions focused on the competencies of understanding, application, analysis, evaluation, and creation of civic literacy. The test served as a powerful tool to determine if the civic literacy of the students has been enhanced.

Teaching UCSP subjects and ensuring the enhancement of civic literacy among students was challenging in the distance learning set-up considering the current problems in the country's distance education. However, the transactional distance learning modality might help enhance the learning outcomes of students in distance education, specifically their civic literacy. Generally, it implied that teaching UCSP through transactional distance learning modality had considerable gaps that the present study would like to address.

Literature Review

This part presents literature and studies that provides a general overview of the nature and context of the research problem focused on distance learning, transactional distance theory, and civic literacy. It includes local and foreign literature and studies that give a deeper understanding of the problem, gap, and scope of the study. The succeeding paragraphs provide the historical background of distance learning, followed by the theories related to this approach, and then the discussions on the similarities and differences of the concepts presented or the synthesis to deeply understand the context of the problem.

Distance Learning

The distance learning modality has a long history. It has several definitions; however, the concept is fundamentally understood as a learning situation wherein students and teachers are physically and geographically separated. This learning modality has been existing long years ago even before the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, this learning modality could be better comprehended and improved by knowing its history and development.

According to Rumble et al. (1986, as cited in Burgess and Russell, 2003), there are four generations of distance learning. The four generations of distance learning are the following: (1.) Correspondence programs or "self-study", (2.) audio, video conferencing, and educational television, (3.) Systems-based distance learning, and (4.) Two-way communications via desktop computers. The first generation, which is the correspondence program, first began in the late 1800s. During this period, printed materials were the method of instruction, and postal services became the communication of teachers and students. Thus, it allowed students in different places to participate in educational opportunities. There were also drawbacks in the implementation of

first-generation distance learning like disruptions of the learning process because of the delayed feedback and interaction. The second generation arose during the advent of audio, video conferencing, and educational television. The improvement in technology allowed more interaction between teachers and students; however, most of the medium at that time was limited to one-way communication. Meanwhile, the continuous advancement and development of technology led to the third generation of distance education. The third-generation setup was characterized by systems-based distance learning which involved multi-media such as print, audio, and video linked with interaction through phone and face-to-face. Thus, it allowed more interaction between the teachers and students. Lastly, the fourth generation of distance learning is the current and more advanced modality compared to the three previous generations. It consists of two-way communication via desktop computers and cutting-edge technologies such as virtual reality. Teachers and students are linked with audio technology or by virtual chat rooms. With this setup, a real-time video conversation and chat are possible, so it allows them to have ease in communication.

From the aforementioned generations of distance learning, the fourth generation is considered the existing distance education modality in the Philippines during the pandemic. Previously, distance learning in the country was immediately implemented because of the restrictions of the face-to-face learning modality and technology became one of the resources with huge help in battling the challenges of distance learning. However, there is a trivial difference between the implementation of distance learning nowadays compared to its implementation in the fourth generation. Distance learning before has been offered as an option for students' preferences while at present, distance learning has become the only learning modality in the new normal education. The Department of Education in the Philippines has left with a single option to pursue

education and that is through distance learning. Moreover, educational institutions have to cater to a vast number of students in this new normal setup compared to distance education before the pandemic so the possible effects of catering to vast numbers of students in distance education are still undetermined. Therefore, it became a challenge for educators how to implement distance learning without sacrificing the quality of education.

Another definition of distance learning was discussed by Simonson et al. (2019), who stated that distance learning is an institution-based formal education where the students are physically and geographically separated, and interactive telecommunications systems are used to connect students, resources, and teachers. According to him, there are four elements of distance learning: (1.) institution-based, (2.) separation of teachers and students, (3.) interactive communications, and (4.) connecting the students, resources, and teachers. First is the institution-based, which differs from distance learning to self-study, an institution could be a traditional educational school or college where they offer students education even without attending traditional classrooms. Second is the separation of teachers and students, which is not limited to physical separation but also refers to the separation of time. For instance, a certain instruction or task is offered to students where they can access or obtain it at any time or at their most convenient time; this setup is also called asynchronous distance education. Another thing that separates teachers and students is the intellectual separation. Simonson et al. (2019) posited that teachers have a deeper understanding of the concepts displayed in the course rather than students. So, there is a gap between the knowledge of students and teachers on the presented topic. Hence, the elimination of this separation is one of the goals of distance education for the students to acquire the needed concepts or skills. The third element is interactive communication where interaction is described as vital in distance learning. Interactive communication could be performed by teachers

with their students at a similar time (synchronous) or a different time (asynchronous). It is also essential that students have the means to interact with one another through the help of various resources such as electronic media and most importantly with the teacher's guidance. The last element is the importance of connecting the students, resources, and teachers. In the last element, it was reiterated that the teachers should ensure interaction with the students and must guarantee that the resources used would encourage learning.

Furthermore, the students must be exposed to instructional design that promotes learning and resources that could be observed, felt, heard, or accomplished. According to Simonson et al. (2019), instructional design is the core principle of effective distance learning. Thus, instructional design is one of the crucial elements of distance learning. It needs to be adequately crafted for the students to be motivated in the synchronous and asynchronous modalities and could still grasp the lesson even if they are not in a traditional face-to-face setup. Consequently, the elements of distance education presented by Simonson et al. (2019) could be considered in improving the country's implementation of distance learning. The following concepts may be examined: (1.) Institution-based, the capacity of the school or institution to handle the vast number of students in the distance education setup; (2.) Separation of students and teachers, an intervention or technique may be utilized to lessen the negative impact of physical and time separation between students and teachers, for instance, providing support to the students when assigned with tasks or lessons during asynchronous setup; (3.) Interactive communications, various platforms could be used to maintain and enhance the communications and connections between teachers, students, and the materials used; and (4.) Contemplation of instructional design which suits the needs of the learners, since instructional design in distance education is vital for the student's acquisition of knowledge and

skills, then it must highly promote learning and lessen the separations between teachers and students.

One of the most notable theories is the Transactional Distance by Michael G. Moore. His concept of distance education is simply a representation of an independent study of learners. For him, transactional distance is the typology of all education programs having a different characteristic of separation of teacher and learner. He further reiterated the importance of dialogue, structure, and learners' autonomy in his transactional distance learning theory. Primarily, according to Moore, there is a separation happening between teachers and students. It does not only refer to physical separation, but it is a situation wherein a "space or separation" has been created between teacher and student because of the differences in behavior being possessed by both parties. Moore coined the term psychological and communication space or gap as the main concepts in transactional distance theory. The psychological space refers to the cognitive aspect which tells more about the understanding of each side (teacher and student) during the teaching-learning process. In contrast, the communication space has something to do with how the instruction or content of a specific course is delivered to the student. Furthermore, Moore's theory is composed of two elements, first is the dialogue, which pertains to the provision for two-way communication and the second is the structure which relates to the extent of a program if it is responsive and not responsive to the learner's needs. For him, these two elements could be measured in the practice of distance learning modality. He also mentioned that the learner's autonomy plays a vital role in the distance learning setup. The student must take a high degree of responsibility for the conduct of the learning program because distance learning offers limited teacher guidance unlike in traditional settings where the students are very dependent on the teacher. On the other hand, the program structure must also be examined to ensure that it could provide for the needs of the

students. This is somehow similar to the idea of Simonson et al. (2019) who also recognized the vital role of instructional design or structure of the distance learning modality to achieve successful acquisition of learning competencies. The aforementioned concepts both highlighted the importance of the development of an instructional design that would encourage interaction between students and teachers. Thus, considering Moore's idea on the dialogue, structure, and learner's autonomy in the current distance learning modality implemented in the country would be helpful to improve the effectiveness of the present learning modality.

Another theory that supports the idea of Moore is the Theory of Independent Study by Charles Wedemeyer (1981, as cited in Simonson et al., 2019). The theory stated the importance of the student's independence which is similar to Moore's learner's autonomy. However, it highlighted the utilization of technology as means to achieve independence. According to Wedemeyer (cited in Simonson et al., 2019), there are 10 characteristics that the system (distance learning) must consider to fulfill the students' independent learning with the help of technology. The 10 characteristics are the following: (1) having the capacity to operate at any place where there are students, (2.) having more responsibility for the education of the students, (3.) removing the custodial-type duties of teachers so that more time could be given to genuinely educational tasks, (4.) provide more options in courses, formats, and methods to the students, (5.) adaptation of the teaching methods and media that have been proved effective ,(6.) consider blending different techniques and media in teaching so that the subject could be delivered in the best way, (7.) revisit and redesign the courses offered to suit into an "articulated media program" , (8.) adaptation to individual differences must conserve and intensify, (9.) students' evaluation of achievement must be simple and not by putting restrictions concerning the place, rate, method, or sequence of student study, and (10) let the students learn at their own pace. Consequently, the ideas of Wedemeyer are

comparable to Moore's dialogue, structure, and autonomy. His thoughts on the application of technology and redesigning the offered courses for the accuracy of the program are greatly related to Moore's idea on the distance learning "structure" which focuses on providing suitable content and methods to fulfill the learning needs of students. In addition, Moore and Wedemeyer have the same concept regarding students' autonomy or responsibilities because they both believe that students must take a high sense of responsibility and control with their studies for them to be successful.

Furthermore, it has been almost two years since the majority of the educational institutions worldwide are practicing distance learning due to the pandemic. Shifting to distance learning modality without ample time to prepare and to be familiar with the new setup and crafts in distance education is difficult for educational institutions, teachers, and learners. Based on the preceding concepts of Moore and Wedemeyer, distance education involves dialogue (student and teacher interaction), structure or the instructional design and contents of the program, and the students' autonomy or independence which are the most crucial elements to consider in implementing effective distance learning modality. Since the implementation of distance learning throughout the pandemic, various foreign and local researches have been conducted to explore the nature and effects of extensive distance learning during the pandemic.

Hebebcı et al. (2020) conducted a study that showed the views of students and teachers on distance education practices during the pandemic. The findings displayed that the students and teachers have positive and negative opinions about distance education. Some students did not feel that distance education separated them from one another while other students are dissatisfied with distance learning because they do not understand the subject. After all, the teacher has inadequate discussion, insufficient time, and lack of technology. In contrast, teachers view distance learning

positively. They have emphasized the positive aspects of distance learning and the significance of maintaining education. Also, they highlighted the importance of different distance education modalities such as online and modular modalities for it to give equal opportunities to students. The study also emphasized the relevance of educational activities in the distance learning modality. They have anticipated that the courses and programs designed with various models for distance education will become more and more popular. So, they thought that their study would shed light on another study about the design and use of distance education environments at all levels of education. Considering the ideas and recommendations of the foregoing study, it is one of the objectives of the present study to utilize and evaluate the possible distance learning model suitable for the distance learning setup.

Meanwhile, several studies and articles outlined the advantages and disadvantages of distance learning amidst the pandemic. The Consortium for North American Higher Education Collaboration (2020) stated the benefits of online learning in a COVID-19 world and beyond. Some of the stated advantages are: it is flexible, online degrees are more affordable, it is accessible, it develops essential skills, and allows customized learning experience. Thus, it could be realized that distance learning somehow became the solution to continue giving education to the students despite the challenges that educational institutions might face because of the pandemic.

In addition, the adoption of distance learning in some countries during the pandemic gained positive feedback from teachers and students. El Refae et al. (2020) conducted a study about the faculty and students' satisfaction, opportunities, and challenges in distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in UAE. The study mentioned that distance learning is an effective way to ensure and continue the learning process of academic institutions, specifically in preventing the spread of the virus. The findings revealed that the teachers and students perceived distance learning

as having the potential to enhance their ICT skills, support work, and education simultaneously, and provide quality education and innovations that enable learners to learn anytime and anywhere. So, it could be concluded that distance learning in times of pandemic could still help the students receive the quality education they deserved.

Another study that shows a positive outcome of distance learning is the study of Lall and Singh (2020). The study was conducted to understand the perspective, attitudes, and readiness of students in the online class setup at the university level in the country of India. It is an observational descriptive study and among the 200 students being asked, 74% stated that they preferred to study through online classes. The reasons given are because of the flexibility of time in studies; they can study anytime they want. Also, the majority of the students are satisfied with the content and method of online teaching. Around 30% of the students stated that they prefer the lecture delivered through a PPT with an audio recording. However, there are some problems that the students perceive and these are the lack of co-curricular activities in the online mode of attending classes and there is no sufficient communication with the teachers. Therefore, one of the things to be considered in distance learning is having enough time to communicate with students.

However, not all studies about distance learning have the same positive outcome. Kaya and Onder (2002) identified that in distance education, a high level of interaction and social communication cannot be achieved easily compared to face-to-face instruction. The study stated that teachers are dissatisfied with distance learning because of insufficient interaction with students. Therefore, in distance learning it is necessary to have proper communication and interaction with the students for it may help them improve their understanding and learnings in a specific subject they are taking. Lastly, considering Moore's idea of dialog in distance learning would be a great help.

Another study showing drawbacks of distance education is the study of Baris and Cankaya (2016). The study is about the opinions of academic staff teaching common and compulsory courses through distance education in Turkey. They have posited the following disadvantages of teaching through distance learning: lack of communication, motivational predicaments, lack of technological devices, low level of students' readiness, lack of effective lectures, and weak feedback. It was also shown in the study that teachers emphasized the motivation problem. They find it difficult to motivate the students in the distance learning setup. However, Baris and Cankaya concluded that these issues could be lessened by developing software and hardware skills for academic teachers teaching common compulsory courses through distance education. They even suggested having a training session on Learning Management System (LMS) and online class arrangements for both teachers and students before opening the academic term. Hence, with the current distance learning setup in the country, educational institutions should also consider the suggested ideas by Baris and Cankaya to improve and lessen the issues of distance learning modality.

Transactional Distance Learning

Considering the ideas of Moore, there are studies conducted and applied to the transactional distance concepts in a distance learning class. Abuhassna and Yahaya (2018) studied students' utilization of distance learning through an interventional online module based on Moore's transactional distance theory. It was conducted in the University College of Applied Sciences in Palestine through experimental research design. The main goal of their study is to investigate the efficacy of an interventional online module based on Moore's transactional distance theory on students' learning autonomy and satisfaction regarding the utilization of distance learning. Based on the study, there is a significant difference in the realm of instructor support before and after the

intervention within the intervention group. It was also found that there is no significant difference in the mean scores for students' collaboration and interaction, satisfaction, and learning autonomy within the intervention group before and after the intervention. Abuhassna and Yahaya posited that distance education modality is effective in the education and learning system in terms of the following: understanding, remembering, and some of the processes required in the systematic stages of education. It also disclosed that there were no substantial differences within and between the two methods (online and face-to-face), which means that students in online courses exhibit good results in conjunction with face-to-face groups. In line with this, it could be concluded that the concept of Moore's transactional distance had effects if it will be applied in the teaching-learning process in a distance learning setup. That is why the researcher is interested if the same result will be gained if Moore's concept of dialogue, structure, and autonomy will be integrated into teaching a specific subject like UCSP in a distance learning modality. It will also attempt to determine if it is effective not only under the level of understanding and remembering in Bloom's Taxonomy but as well as applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating ideas.

Garry Falloon from the University of Waikato also conducted a study titled "*Making the Connection: Moore's Theory of Transactional Distance and Its Relevance to the Use of a Virtual Classroom in Postgraduate Online Teacher Education*". He used Moore's concepts of Transactional Distance in examining the efficacy of using the virtual classroom to promote quality dialogue and explored how both internal and external structural elements related to the purpose and use of the classroom affected the learner's sense of autonomy. The study adopted an interpretive case study methodology and utilized a range of data-collection tools consistent with qualitative studies. Falloon illustrated the complexity of the relationship that exists between the elements of Moore's theory, and how the implementation of an external structuring technology

such as the virtual classroom, can have both positive impacts (dialogue creation) and negative impacts (diminished sense of learner autonomy). The findings of the study stated the following: (a) the use of a virtual classroom can add up to the enhancement of quality dialogue. However, it can be considered a double-edged sword, in a way that it has a positive effect on structural aspects and has a negative effect on students' autonomy; (b) because of the nature of synchronous class in a virtual classroom, it affects the students in engaging a purposeful dialogue. There are participants of the study who stated that they felt hesitant to participate for the reason that the environment in a virtual classroom does not have enough time to generate their comments or input and they do not want to run the risk of "looking silly" in front of their peers; (c) the theory of Moore needs for a workable balance to be struck between students' autonomy and course structure so that the students could maintain a sense of empowerment and ownership of the learning, also, the structure of the course must provide enough direction and the standards and expectations of performance should be clearly communicated; and (d) the last factor that affects the participant's ability to engage in dialogue is the impact of technical and infrastructural issues such as the quality of broadband, computer equipment of adequate specification, and the students' level of technical competence. Overall, the study provided an important measure of the efficacy of using the virtual classroom to enhance quality dialogue, while at the same time identifying areas where the theory may need reconsidering in light of the arrival of digital technologies and online learning to the distance learning landscape. Hence, applying Moore's transactional distance constructs such as dialogue, structure, and autonomy may have different effects if it will be applied to various teaching-learning setups and levels of students. In this study, the constructs of Moore will be integrated into the teaching of UCSP subject to the Grade12 students in a distance learning modality. This is somehow similar to the study conducted by Falloon for he used a virtual classroom in the integration of

Moore's concept of dialogue, structure, and autonomy. Lastly, the effect of teaching UCSP using the concepts of dialogue and structure will then be evaluated after the semester.

Distance Learning in the Philippines and its Challenges During Pandemic

In the Philippines, distance learning is not a new concept even before the pandemic. Back in 2009, the Department of Education created and implemented an Internet-Based Education Program (DepEd memorandum no. 169, S. 2009) and Open High School Program (DO 46, S. 2006) to cater to remote learning. The program aimed to make distance learning possible for high school students who want to study at their own pace even without attending a traditional classroom. At that time, distance learning was regarded as an alternative offer to students who could not afford or attend normal face-to-face learning. Thus, as an alternative modality, distance learning was not given much focus and innovations. Then all of the sudden, due to the widespread pandemic, distance learning became the new normal learning setup of all country's educational institutions. However, the full adoption of distance learning during the pandemic brought positive and negative perspectives from teachers, students, and other stakeholders.

In the country, there were several studies made describing the outcomes, perceptions, challenges and experiences of the teachers and students in distance learning modality. Barrot et al. (2021) discussed the online learning challenges encountered by students during pandemic and how they cope up with them. Studies revealed that the learning environment at home is their greatest challenge while technological literacy and competency was their least challenge. The findings stated that the Covid-19 pandemic impacted the quality of the learning experience and mental health of the students. With this situation, the abrupt changes of the learning modalities during the pandemic has really affected not only the teachers but also the students. Thus, it is a challenge to

the education sector and all its stakeholders to further study the suitable learning modalities in this time of pandemic.

A year after the advent of Covid-19 pandemic, Aguilar et al. (2021) conducted a study about the learning experiences of the social sciences students in De La Salle University, Dasmariñas branch after a year of online classes. There are four major findings which states that: (1) though students has a gadgets and stable connection, however, glitches occurs due to the prolonged and frequency usage and multiple users in their home, (2) the university has a policy on assessments and schedules and it is helpful but, students revealed that with their average of seven classes, the total number of the assessments overwhelmed them, (3) faculty are helpful and approachable but there is a considerable number of faculty who does not reply to students messages which made them postulate that online learning is moderately effective, and (4) students conveyed the need for presence and connection to teachers through extra curricular activities which is fun and not purely academics. Therefore, there are a lot of things to consider in order to improve the learnings of students in an online distance learning set-up. Educators and stakeholders in education must examine holistically the positive and negative side of conducting this type of modality for the better execution and effects to students learning.

Another study was conducted by Aguilar and Torres in 2021, it is titled “Making Sense of Online Classes during Quarantine due to the Covid-19 Pandemic: Students’ Perceptions from a Philippine University. It also tackles the learning experiences of students towards online set-up and aims to help in devising innovative pedagogical approaches leading to creation of effective online learning spaces (Aguilar and Torres, 2021). Findings stated that there are four self-perceived challenges in online learning and these are technological and infrastructural difficulties, individual readiness, instructional struggles, and domestic barriers. Aguilar and Torres also

suggested that there is a need for re-evaluation and modification of current online learning guidelines to meet the aforementioned issues and develop an authentic model for technology driven and care-centered education based on the challenges and recommendations of the students. Therefore, there is really a need to consider re-evaluating the modalities being used in online learning to help address the needs and problems of students pertaining to online learning. The researcher also considered these aspects in the execution of transactional distance learning modality of UCSP students in the University of Makati.

Junsay and Madrigal (2021) studied the insights and experiences of social science teachers about the challenges and benefits of facilitating online learning in times of the Covid-19 pandemic. The study is limited to the teacher's perspectives. Based on the results, the majority of the respondents believe that the new setup in education is a challenging task for teachers. The following reasons have been given: it requires lots of patience, perseverance, technical training, and extensive planning of the instructional procedure. In addition, the teachers, particularly social science teachers, encountered challenges in online teaching, such as personal, technical, and teaching strategies. They also have difficulty motivating students to engage in the online class activities and submission of outputs. Thus, it can be concluded that the teachers in distance learning have a lot of responsibilities to take, and being the conductor of learning it is necessary to exert efforts in devising and teaching the lessons that might help boost the students to become motivated with their studies. Also, educational institutions must consider the concepts of Moore in transactional distance learning theory which is conducting thorough planning in the structure of the specific program which might help the students achieve the quality of learning despite the current situation.

Meanwhile, Ignacio (2020) also studied the problems faced by teachers, students, and institutions during online classes. The data collected were taken from 29 institutions in various parts of the country. There are twenty-two (22) private schools, universities, and colleges; and seven (7) are state colleges and universities (SUCs) and/or local colleges and universities (LUCs) located in Metro Manila, Cavite, Laguna, Bulacan, Batangas, and Lanao Del Norte. On the other hand, 62% of the respondents are educators and 38% were combined students from different levels (primary, junior, senior high school, and tertiary). His findings showed that online classes had caused various problems for students and teachers, from lack of technology to mental health concerns. Among the technological concerns they encountered are: weak to no internet connection; there is no or sharing of suitable devices (laptop or desktop) for attending online classes, creating, and submitting outputs; lack of expertise in using digital technologies; and lack of knowledge on methods of conducting and attending online classes. Aside from technological concerns, they also encountered the following: students need to go outside the house to purchase a load for them to join the class, online classes made the students feel the heavy workload and requirements, and some students experienced anxiety and depression. Moreover, teachers need additional time and effort because online consultations and communication with students usually exceed the regular class hours and it takes extra work in monitoring students. They also felt tired and stressed, especially for teachers who are not used to being glued to their seats while teaching, unlike the classroom setup. Therefore, to ensure the effectiveness of distance learning, a lot of things should be considered starting from the planning of strategies, technological aspects, emotional aspects, and even the socio-economic status of students and teachers.

In addition, Moralista and Oducado (2020) conducted research about faculty perception toward online education in one of the state colleges in the Philippines during a pandemic, and they

identified that most teachers had average computer competency and had no training in online teaching, with only a few having a very stable internet connection. Also, the teachers perceived that online education resulted in more academic dishonesty, impersonality, and lack of feeling compared to face-to-face classes. Consequently, one thing to recognize in distance learning modality is giving proper training to teachers which would help them improve their technical knowledge and techniques in handling distance learning approaches so that they could deliver the lessons effectively to the students. Moreover, Rotas and Cahapay (2020) findings showed specific difficulties encountered by students and teachers in remote learning and these are unstable internet connectivity, inadequate learning resources, electric power interruptions, vague learning contents, overloaded lesson activities, limited teacher scaffolds, poor peer communication, conflict with home responsibilities, poor learning environment, financial related problems, physical health compromises, and mental health struggles. Thus, the results of the aforementioned studies manifest the impediments to the implementation of distance learning. However, it could somehow lessen its drawbacks if the institutions and educators would consider all the problems and factors that could affect the learning experiences and outcomes of students in a distance learning setup. Based on the findings and recommendations of the previously mentioned researchers and by considering the theoretical concepts of Moore, redesigning the program structure or subject contents of the specific course and allowing flexible communication of students would somehow improve the effectiveness of the distance learning modality.

One of the subjects offered in the school year 2021- 2022 at the Senior High school level is Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP). The fundamental goal of this subject is to enhance the civic literacy of the students to know their basic rights and obligations as citizens of the country and participate in society actively. Following the Department of Education (DepED)

K to 12 Curriculum for Senior High School, the UCSP subject comprises the concepts from the three social sciences fields: Anthropology, Sociology, and Political Science. The subjects integrate the concepts from the three fields to develop the students' awareness of cultural, social, and political dynamics and sensitivity to cultural diversity. These also help students understand how culture, human agency, society, and politics work and engage students in examining the country's current human development goals. Specifically, the integration of the aforesaid concepts in the subject UCSP aimed to improve students' civic literacy through the inculcation of human cultures, human agency, society, politics, cultural relativism, social inclusiveness, prejudices, and social and cultural competence, communities, networks, and institutions. Hence, UCSP comprises the competencies of civic education that are required to be taught by the UCSP teachers to enhance the students' civic literacy. So, by taking the subject, it is expected that the students must possess civic literacy or at least have the knowledge in understanding the cultural, social, and political aspects of our society and have skills in participating in a democratic society. Accordingly, the intended purpose of the course is the enhancement of the students' civic literacy.

Civic Literacy

The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (2018) defines civic education as all the processes that affect people's beliefs, commitments, capabilities, and actions as members or prospective community members. One of the main objectives of civic education is to expose students to knowledge in understanding society's cultural, social, and political aspects to have knowledge and skills in participating in the community they live in. In that way, it would help students to gain more civic literacy. The term "literacy" possesses many definitions, but the fundamental meaning of this word pertains to an individual who can read and write.

Notably, UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2018) defines literacy as the capability to do the following: recognize, comprehend, elucidate, generate, communicate and compute, using printed and written materials associated with varying contexts. Thus, to become a literate individual the capabilities mentioned above should be visible to a person. That's why in education, literacy does not only mean reading and writing. Sauntson (2020) explained that it serves as the driving factor in all subject areas. A student is literate if they can interpret, react, articulate, and express their thoughts. But above all this, Best (2014) posited that civic literacy plays an indispensable role in transforming students into socially engaged citizens. Reading and writing mean keeping up with current events, communicating effectively, and understanding the issues that are shaping the world. Thus, civic literacy could mean understanding, communicating, and participating in cultural, social, and political concepts and undertakings.

At present, UCSP is one of the courses that provide civic education for senior high schools in the Philippines. This course aimed to help the students grow, live, and participate in a diverse society. Also, the course promotes civic literacy which is considered one of the 21st-century skills necessary to learn to participate in civic life. The California State University, Monterey Bay (2005), defines civic literacy as knowledge, skills, and attitudes that students need to work effectively in a diverse society to create more just and equitable workplaces, communities, and social institutions. Thus, learning civic literacy has broad aspects to consider. Among these facets to look for are knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

Moreover, it was also mentioned by McCabe et al. (2016) that civic literacy has three components such as civic dispositions, civic skills, and civic knowledge. Civic dispositions are the values of individuals which allow them to have a more comprehensive understanding of the common good. While listening, speaking, gathering information, advocating, and organizing a

community were all civic skills. Based on this definition, it can be concluded that these skills could be the basis for describing the literacy skills of a person, specifically the senior high school students of the University of Makati taking up the UCSP course.

Furthermore, according to Gould et al. 2011, these skills encourage critical thinking and cooperation, which must involve efficiency in the democratic process. Lastly, civic knowledge consists of comprehending the underlying structures of the government, its operations, and democratic ideas like the rights of individuals and separation of power. Therefore, an individual must possess civic literacy to function well and participate in society. This was supported by Morgan (2016), who asserted about developing civic literacy and efficacy, he mentioned that today's youth is not ready and doesn't have much concern about citizenship and civic learning challenges. Hence, those components of civic literacy in the course UCSP are needed to be learned especially by students nowadays.

On the other hand, Adarlo (2017) stated that Filipinos need to include a global dimension to citizenship education. She reiterated that the Filipino people have to be educated not only to become knowledgeable of the global contexts that affect humanity and the environment but also to act on the negative influences of globalization and make the most of its interests. She even stated that there is a challenge in educating the Filipino people to become critically aware of their history. To resolve this, Adarlo suggested service learning as a useful way of teaching that can bring on a critical approach to citizenship education. The following benefits can be achieved; it can answer the challenge of educating Filipinos for a compassionate, humane, and grassroots globalization, and through aspiring toward a university-community partnership, critical service learning could make students, academe, and communities in solidarity toward social change.

Synthesis

The literature and studies presented above are significant to the construction of the present study since these provide an impression of the research problem that this study addressed. The aforesaid literature and studies, from previous to current, provided an understanding of the scope, nature, and gap of the research topic. Initially, some studies presented the importance of distance learning and its negative and positive impacts on teaching and learning. The history and generations of distance learning have already been discussed by scholars; they stated that distance education nowadays is in the fourth generation of distance learning where more advanced modality is practiced via desktop computers and cutting-edge technologies such as virtual reality. The scope of the present study focused mainly on distance learning and similar studies had given findings about distance learning, specifically its impact on students and teachers. According to the studies, some teachers and students had difficulty dealing with distance learning because of reasons such as lack of technical ability and capacity and because of insufficient interaction in online learning (Baris & Cankaya, 2016; Kaya & Onder, 2022). Similarly, the distance learning interaction is one of the concerns of the present study because the researcher views that this may affect the motivation of the students in the distance modality based on Moore's Theory. The present study would like to identify an efficient model of distance learning since there were several drawbacks to the implementation of distance learning in the past years as mentioned. Also, this study supports the findings of Morgan (2016) about civic literacy that today's youth is not ready and doesn't have much concern about citizenship and civic learning hence it aims to help students with the acquisition of civic literacy through an efficient distance learning approach.

Most of the previous studies focused on the impact of distance learning, specifically its negative and positive effects on students and teachers; however, they did not cover the approach

to achieving interactive and efficient online learning. Previous studies deliberated the needs of students and teachers in the online modality including perseverance, technical training, and extensive planning of the instructional procedure (Junsay & Madrigal, 2021), and discussed challenges that students and teachers encountered such as the lack of communication, motivational predicaments, lack of technological devices, low level of students' readiness, lack of effective lectures, and weak feedback (Baris & Cankaya, 2016). On the other hand, the present study focused on the negative and positive impact of distance learning, hence it used the previous findings about the factors that affected distance learning and the Transactional Distance Theory of Moore to create an efficient distance learning model that could increase the engagements and help students enhance knowledge acquisition in the distance learning set-up.

The negative and positive impact of distance learning was already identified by the previous studies but resolutions about enhancing the distance learning experience of students and what approach could be done to help students and teachers cope with the negative impacts of distance learning was not yet identified. Hence, it served as the research gap of the study. Consequently, this study determined the efficiency of the Transactional Distance Learning approach in enhancing the learning experiences of students particularly enhancing their civic literacy in UCSP subjects. This also proposed a model of distance learning that could incite interaction and could enhance the civic literacy of students.

Teaching and ensuring interaction among students are challenging in the distance learning set-up considering the current problems in the country's distance education. However, Moore's concept of transactional distance learning may help enhance the learning experience and outcomes of students in distance education. Hence it needs to be applied and examined. Findings about the efficiency of the Transactional Distance Learning approach in providing effective and meaningful

learning experiences to students are highly significant because they could help decrease some of the drawbacks of distance learning and a lack of interaction. Also, the output of the study, specifically the transactional model will help the students and teacher to have a better online learning experience. The present study assumed that the transactional distance learning modality may enhance the civic literacy of students based on its constructs.

Theoretical Framework

This part discusses the theoretical framework on which the study is anchored. The theoretical framework is the construction or guide that helps to hold or support a theory of a research study (Sacred Heart University Library, 2020). The theory will be explained and connected to the problem and findings of the present study.

This study links to the “Transactional Distance Theory” by Michael G. Moore, one of the scholars who studied distance education. In 1972, Moore published the first statement of the theory about distance education and first formulated it in 1997 (Born, 2011). Distance education at first impression could be thought of as a situation in an educational system in delivering instructions where the students are physically separated from the teacher. However, Moore (1997) stated that distance education is not just about the physical separation of teachers and learners but it is more about the method and practice of teaching. The general concept of his theory describes more the situation of a teacher and learner engaged in an educational relationship. He pointed out that the strategy used by the teacher in delivering instructions could result in a distance or separation between the learner and teacher. He further described it as a "transaction" or "transactional distance" which refers to the situation or problem in a teaching-learning process wherein the teacher and student could create misunderstanding when it comes to the delivery of instruction.

Moore's idea of the transaction has been derived from Dewey's notion in which the transaction refers to the following concepts: the interaction among the surroundings, the individuals, and the patterns of behavior in a situation (Moore, 1997). Conversely, in Moore's theory, the transaction refers to distance education. It is a situation wherein a "space or separation" has been created between teacher and student because of the differences in behavior being possessed by both parties. Moore coined the term psychological and communication space or gap as the main concepts in transactional distance theory. The psychological space refers to the cognitive aspect which tells more about the understanding of each side (teacher and student) during the teaching-learning process while the communication space has something to do with how the instruction or content of a specific course is delivered to the student. To fully understand how the "transactional distance" happens in a teaching-learning process, he further stated that there are three factors that directly affect the psychological and communication gap between the learner and teacher, and these are: dialogue, structure, and autonomy.

The first construct of the theory is his idea of "dialogue". It is when teachers and learners interact with one another, like when the teacher gives instruction and the student responds, then a dialogue is developed (Moore, 1997). The main goal of the dialogue is to improve the understanding of the student in a teaching-learning relationship. Moore posited that this is the most essential part of the relationship of student and teacher for it requires interaction with expected qualities in the level of conversation such as both parties should be actively participating, dialogue should be meaningful, encouraging, has the willingness to listen and share thoughts, and lastly, both of them must be appreciative. Another role of dialogue in the educational relationship is that it affects the level of understanding of a student in the learning process depending on the quality of dialogue developed between teacher and student. The more dialogue exhibited, the less

transactional distance. This means that dialogue helps to bridge the psychological and communication gap in a distance-education. Furthermore, Moore also discussed the importance of the medium of communication to be used in dialogue set-up and the significance of manipulating communication media to increase the quality of dialogue between student and teacher. He explained the different impacts of the medium of communication in a teaching-learning process and how it affects the quality of dialogue or interaction between the teacher and student. One of the examples that he gave is when the lesson has been delivered through television, an audiotape, or a “teach-yourself book”. There is no dialogue between teacher and student in this type of media for the mentioned medium cannot bring messages back to the teacher. Therefore, great transactional distance has been formed because students have no way to interact with the teacher. On the other hand, mediums like printed self-study materials, audiotapes, or videotapes could still promote dialogue because of the student’s internal or silent reaction with the one who organized and set the contents of the materials which is called "virtual dialogue". Meanwhile, Moore also stated that though some mediums cannot have the ideal dialogue, manipulatively choosing a highly interactive one like "electronic teleconference media" would likely break the transactional distance more effectively for it promotes a more collaborative and subjective conversation on the part of teacher and student. In line with this, the researcher is looking forward to Moore's concept of dialogue as one of the parameters in identifying if the transactional learning approach in teaching UCSP courses through distance learning modality would help students to increase their civic literacy. It will also attempt to determine if designing a lesson plan and learning modules anchored on Moore's dialogue will encourage students to become more participative and to listen attentively in class discussions that may affect the enhancement of their civic literacy.

The second construct of the theory is the "structure". This is the second factor that determines the transactional distance in the teaching-learning process. Structure refers to the elements in the course design or how the teaching program is structured so that it can be delivered through the different communications media (Moore, 1997). This construct of the theory states that great transactional distance will be created if the structure of the course or program in the educational system has been highly structured. On the other hand, if the structure of the course or program is minimally structured it will minimize the transactional distance. A highly structured program based on the concept of Moore refers to the way the learning materials have been designed. If it is more detailed and everything is already presented, thus, it requires minimal dialogue or interaction between student and teacher; in that case, a high transactional distance will be formed. While a minimally structured course or the program will lessen the transactional distance if it is designed properly based on the needs of the students and the contents must still require interactions, also, it should not be pre-determined according to Moore. Medium use in delivering the lesson is also a factor. For instance, using technology like computers and self-study printed materials with properly structured content will likely minimize the transactional distance for it promotes more interactive dialogue between students and teachers. In the present study, the concept of "structure" will be applied by teaching the UCSP subject in which the program or flow of the lesson plan in every synchronous class is structured based on the needs of the students. In this way, it would create a dialogue or more student-teacher interactions and thus leads to breaking the transactional distance. Lastly, the researcher would examine whether teaching the UCSP subject in a structured program (highly structured lesson plan and learning modules) would help the students enhance their civic literacy skills.

Finally, the third construct of transactional distance theory is the learner's autonomy. Moore (1997) described autonomy as the extent to which the learner exerts control over learning procedures. It tells about the individual responsibility of the students in the learning process. Giving judgments and taking decisions about strategies for studying are some of the responsibilities the students must possess in a distance education set-up. Moore pointed out that even if the course or program is highly or minimally structured if there is no dialogue, the learner will need to decide for himself what strategies he will be using for his study. In other words, the autonomy of the learner will need to be exercised more if there will be a large amount of transactional distance. Concerning the present study, the concept of learner autonomy will be considered as one factor affecting the learning of the students, specifically the enhancement of their civic literacy. The researcher will examine the presence of learner autonomy, specifically the student's strategies in learning the course through the tasks and activities to be done by the students during asynchronous learning.

Therefore, dialogue, structure, and autonomy are factors that have a connection to the transactional distance happening in a teaching-learning process. These three variables should be contemplated in distance education for these variables have a role in how to break the transactional distance in a teaching-learning process. The quality of dialogue must be considered for the more the student and teacher interact, the lesser the transactional distance is. Also, properly structured materials or programs that are not predetermined will promote interactions in a teaching-learning process while the autonomy of the students has a great impact in breaking the transactional distance, especially in the educational system wherein there is less dialogue and a minimally structured program or course. Consequently, Moore's Transactional Distance theory is relevant to the present study because it would help the researcher to determine the effectiveness of

transactional distance learning modality in the enhancement of civic literacy of Grade 12 senior high school students at the University of Makati in taking up the course Understanding Culture, Society and Politics. The concepts of the theory would be a great guide in determining the basis for creating a transactional distance learning model in teaching the course UCSP. In the proposed study, the researcher will integrate the following constructs from the theory: (1) Dialogue between the teacher and students to help them enhance their civic literacy by applying Moore's dialogue in the teaching-learning process. (2) Structure. Applying a structured program such as a lesson plan and learning modules in teaching the UCSP subject that could break or create a transactional distance in a teaching-learning process and determine its effect on the student's enhancement of civic literacy. (3) Student's autonomy. Allowing the students to use their strategies in studying the subject to help them break the transactional distance and enhance their civic literacy. Hence all three concepts will be integrated into this study that would be useful in identifying the effectiveness of distance learning in the enhancement of the civic literacy of the students.

To further explain how the transactional distance theory will work in the study, a diagrammatic illustration of the process in the form of a research paradigm was designed as shown below.

Research Paradigm

The objective of this study is to determine the effectiveness of the Transactional Distance Learning Modality in enhancing the civic literacy of Grade 12 students in distance education. It also aims to identify if the distance learning factors based on this theory of Moore could enhance

the civic literacy of the students. To further understand the illustration above, the following description has been made.

The researcher used the following as inputs for the study: UCSP Instructional Materials such as course syllabus, learning modules, lesson plans, and UCSP Assessment Tools: pre-test and post-test. These inputs served as the basis for studying the effectiveness of distance learning modality in enhancing the civic literacy of the students.

Furthermore, in the process, the researcher administered a preliminary test to the seven (7) Grade 12 UCSP classes and ensured that the two selected groups had similar capabilities before the administration of the treatment. These two selected groups were assigned as the control and experimental group. After the selection of the two groups, both were taught with the UCSP subject through the current distance learning modality of UMak for the entire midterm period, then a pre-test was conducted after the midterm. The data from the pre-test was organized and calculated. Afterward, during the final term, the Transactional Distance Learning was administered to the experimental group while the UMak Distance Learning modality remained as is in the control group. The implementation of the UMak Distance Learning modality included typical synchronous classroom discussion based on the course syllabus and the modular activities were taken from the UCSP module. The student learning strategy under the UMak distance learning modality was mainly dependent on the student's learning style. On the other hand, under Transactional Distance Learning, the following constructs of Moore were integrated into the researcher's lesson plan: Structure. The researcher used the following instructional materials: Graphic organizer, module, Mentimeter, Padlet, Facebook group page, and improvised module wherein the students will be able to have self-paced learning; Dialogue. During synchronous class, the researcher had made sure that every class discussion promoted quality dialogue. The students in every online meeting

had utilized the following strategies in learning: debate, panel discussion, think-pair-share, buzz session, brainstorming, and the Socratic Method. These strategies encourage student-teacher interactions and student-student interaction, motivate students to become more participative in the discussion, listen attentively, and share their thoughts in class. Thus, it may lead to breaking the physical gap between students and teachers in distance learning. Moreover, to consider the autonomy in structuring the lesson plan, the tasks or activities that were given to students required the students to do it on their own, so the teacher just served as a guide on the side. The following tasks or activities were accomplished by the students during asynchronous classes: learning diaries, concept maps, reflective writing, creating a digital newspaper, diagram analysis, and creating FAQ flyers. The post-test was conducted later after the final term and the data from the post-test was organized and calculated. At the end of the process, the data from the pre-test and post-test were analyzed, compared, and interpreted.

Finally, the expected output of this study is to identify the efficacy of the transactional distance learning modality in the enhancement of civic literacy of Grade 12 students and to propose a transactional distance learning model for teaching UCSP subjects.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the efficacy of the Transactional Distance Learning modality in enhancing the civic literacy of Grade 12 senior high school students of the University of Makati in the subject Understanding Culture, Society and Politics (UCSP). Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of civic literacy of the control and experimental groups based on the results of the pre-test?

2. Is there a significant difference between the level of civic literacy of the control and experimental groups based on the results of the pre-test?
3. What is the level of civic literacy of the control and experimental groups based on the result of the post-test?
4. Is there a significant difference between the level of civic literacy of the control and experimental groups based on the results of the post-test?
5. Is there a significant difference between the results of the pre-test and post-test of the control group and experimental groups in UCSP after the utilization of the non-transactional distance learning modality?
6. What transactional distance learning model can be designed to help improve the civic literacy of students in UCSP courses?

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses (Ho) were tested in the study through a 0.05(5%) level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the level of civic literacy of the control and experimental groups based on the results of the pre-test.
2. There is no significant difference between the level of civic literacy of the control and experimental groups based on the results of the post-test.

3. There is no significant difference between the results of the pre-test and post-test of the control group in UCSP after the utilization of the non-transactional distance learning modality.
4. There is no significant difference between the results of the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group in UCSP after the utilization of the transactional distance learning modality.

Significance of the Study

This study aims to determine the efficacy of the Transactional Distance Learning Modality in enhancing the civic literacy of Grade 12 Senior High School Students of the University of Makati in their Understanding Culture, Society and Politics course. Moreover, the results of the study will be beneficial to the following:

Department of Education. The findings could be considered for revisiting the current curriculum guide of the UCSP course and in improving the future curriculum suitable for all types of learning modalities.

Curriculum Designer. The result of the study could help the curriculum designers to design learning materials and educational instruction for UCSP courses using transactional distance learning modality that will help enhance the civic literacy needs of the students.

School Administrators. The findings could add insights on the evaluation and designing of the effective teaching methodology in improving the civic literacy of students in the UCSP course or any specific course.

UMAK Center for Curriculum and Materials Development. The findings could give insights to the CCMD officers on how it can promote and enhance the civic literacy of the students using the transactional distance learning modality.

Teachers. The result of the study could help the teacher understand the civic literacy needs of the students and consider the transactional distance learning modality in teaching UCSP courses to help them enhance their civic literacy.

Students. The findings could help the students enhance their civic literacy needs after taking the UCSP course in a transactional distance learning modality.

Parents. The findings of the study could help the parents of the respondents to have an idea if the distance learning modality is effective in imparting knowledge and skills to their children. This will be their guide in supporting the academic needs of their children.

Future Researchers. The result of the study could give them additional information and ideas to conduct further research in the related field.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study encompassed the efficacy of the Transactional Distance Learning Modality in enhancing the civic literacy of Grade 12 Senior High School Students of the University of Makati in their Understanding Culture, Society and Politics course. Specifically, it determined if the utilization of transactional distance learning enhanced the civic literacy of grade 12 students in the UCSP subject and it proposed a transactional distance learning model to enhance the civic literacy of students in the UCSP subject.

This study was conducted at the Higher School of the University of Makati in the 1st Semester of the School Year 2021-2022. The respondents of the study were the Grade 12 senior high school students who were taking the subject Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics.

Definition of Terms

Autonomy – It is the individual responsibility and strategy of students in learning the course UCSP.

Asynchronous Learning Modality - A learning modality wherein the students and teachers do not meet virtually. Instead, the teacher allows the students to learn on their schedule within a certain timeframe.

Civic Literacy – It is the knowledge, skills, and attitude of the students in participating productively in civic life by knowing how to be informed, understanding governmental systems, and knowing their functions in a society based on political, social, economic, cultural, educational, and religious contexts. It also refers to all the processes that affect students' beliefs, commitments, capabilities, and actions as members of society.

Civic knowledge – The students' understanding of civic life and awareness of their functions in society in terms of the following contexts: political, social, economic, cultural, educational, and religious.

Civic Skills – The students' abilities to actively participate and be responsible citizens in a democratic country. It refers to the student's capability to identify, recognize and understand various issues in the following contexts: political, social, economic, cultural, educational, and religious. (Based on Comber's definition the minimum civic skills are: personal communication

skills, knowledge of political systems, and the ability to think critically about civic and political life)

Dialogue – The level of interaction created between student and teacher during the teaching-learning process in the distance learning modality.

Google Meet - A video-communication service developed by Google. This is used by teachers and students at the University of Makati for the execution of synchronous classes or meetings.

Structure – One of the constructs of Moore in his Transactional Distance Learning theory. It refers to the design and organization of the instructional materials for teaching UCSP subjects.

Synchronous Learning Modality - A learning modality wherein the teachers and students attend a class session virtually at the same time and on the same video communication platform.

TBL Hub - Technology-Based Learning Hub. The official learning management system of the University of Makati.

Transactional Distance – A psychological and communication space or gap between teacher and students that happens in the teaching-learning process. The psychological space refers to the cognitive aspect which tells more about the understanding of each side (teacher and student) during the teaching-learning process while the communication space has something to do with how the instruction or content of a specific course is delivered to the student.

Transactional Learning Modality – A type of teaching instruction and strategy which emphasizes the quality of dialogue or interaction, structure or the design of lesson plan, and the students' autonomy which would help to encourage students to become more participative, listen

attentively, and share their thoughts in class discussions, and could lead the students in enhancing their specific skills in a specific subject.

Transactional Distance Learning Lesson Plan - A lesson plan that is anchored on Moore's transactional distance learning constructs, such as structure, dialogue, and autonomy. This is the lesson plan that was administered to the experimental group.

Transactional Learning Modules - Modified learning modules based on the transactional distance learning constructs of Moore that are created for the experimental group. The learning objectives and assessments of the modules focus on the civic literacy of the students. Each learning assessment has an objective that focuses on the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective aspects of the students.

UCSP - Understanding Culture, Society and Politics. One of the core subjects in the senior high school curriculum.

UMak Distance Learning Modality - The distance learning modality of the University of Makati comprises synchronous and asynchronous classes.

Zoom - A cloud-based video communication application used for video-based meetings. This is also another platform being used by teachers and students at the University of Makati for synchronous meetings.

CHAPTER 2

METHODOLOGY

This chapter comprises the research design and methodology of the study, specifically, the techniques, population frame and sampling scheme, instruments, validation of instruments, data gathering procedures, statistical treatments, and data processing. The methodology helps the researcher to systematically answer the research questions raised in this study. Primarily, the present study focuses on the enhancement of the civic literacy of students through distance learning as a basis for creating a transactional distance learning model in the subject Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP).

Design and Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research design. Quantitative research design is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data and it can be used to find patterns and averages, make predictions, test causal relationships, and generalize results to wider populations (Bhandari, 2020). A quantitative research design is appropriate for this study because the nature of the research questions to be investigated requires numerical data and quantitative interpretation.

The researcher utilized the experimental method, specifically, the Randomized or True Experiment to identify the efficacy of the intervention that was employed in the study. True Experiment is used to describe all studies with at least one independent variable that is experimentally manipulated and with at least one dependent or outcome variable (Salkind, 2010). Moreover, the intervention used in the study was the Transactional Distance Learning modality anchored on Moore's Transactional Distance Theory. Mainly, the intervention was applied to

determine if the civic literacy of Grade 12 senior high school students in the UCSP Subject could be enhanced through the utilization of the transactional distance learning modality. The findings about the efficacy of the intervention in enhancing the civic literacy of students were the basis to create a transactional distance learning model for UCSP. Since the experimental method is considered the "gold standard" in research for its unique strength in its internal validity and because it could link the cause and effect through treatment manipulation in an experimental group (Ostoya, 2015), thus, it was used to determine the efficacy of intervention and to compare the outcomes of the two groups. Subsequently, in the research process, the Transactional Distance Learning modality implemented in the experimental group was executed with lesson plans drafted based on the constructs of Moore's Transactional Distance Theory (dialogue, structure, and autonomy). On the other hand, the control group utilized the current distance learning modality of the University of Makati.

Population Frame and Sampling Scheme

The total population of the incoming Grade 12 students who were taking the Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP) course at the University of Makati for the 1st semester of the Academic Year 2021-2022 was 1, 332 students with the age range of 17-18 years old.

Since the study employed experimental methods, specifically the Randomized or True Experiment, selected respondents were grouped as the experimental and control group. Hence, the sample size only consisted of 70 students in all; 35 in the experimental group and 35 in the control group. The study had 35 participants per group because the regular number of students per class at the University of Makati ranges from 35 to 50. As stated by Charitaka (2015) and Cohen et al. (2007), the minimum number of participants in an experimental study is 1-30 participants, but a

bigger number of participants means better for the research. The selection of the 2 classes was based on their scores in the prelim test to assure that these two groups had the same aptitude. A prelim test was administered to 7 classes and among the 7 classes, only 2 classes with similar or close average scores were selected and assigned as experimental and control groups.

Instruments of the Study

To achieve the objectives of the study, the following instruments were utilized: UCSP Course Syllabus, Learning Modules, Lesson Plans, and Pre-test and Post-test.

Course Syllabus. The UCSP course syllabus was used as a guide in designing the lesson plans for the topics taught to the students.

Learning Modules. The UMak learning modules were both used by the students under control and experimental groups. But, the learning modules that the experimental group utilized had different learning objectives and assessments based on the transactional distance learning constructs of Moore, and part of the objectives was to assess the civic literacy of the students.

Lesson Plans. Six (6) lesson plans were used based on the topics discussed in the final term. However, the researcher developed two types of lesson plans: (1) a traditional lesson plan for the control group and (2) a lesson plan anchored on Moore's transactional distance learning constructs, such as structure, dialogue, and autonomy. Also, the integration of civic literacy was considered in the construction of lesson plans used for the experimental group.

Pre-test and Post-test. The pretest and post-test questionnaires were employed to determine the efficacy of the Transactional Distance Learning modality in enhancing the civic literacy of the students. The pre-test and post-test are two different tests but both consisted of 50 questions. The test questions focused more on situational analysis and real-life situations framed on Bloom's Taxonomy's domains namely comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation since it was used to test the civic literacy of students.

Preparation

The researcher had come up with the following preparations on how the research instruments were administered in the study.

Course Syllabus. The syllabus was prepared by the UCSP teachers in the high school department of UMak. It was created based on the curriculum guide of DepEd before the 1st semester of this school year started.

Learning Modules. The researcher utilized the UMak learning modules. However, modules for the experimental group were enhanced by the researcher following Moore's Transactional Distance Theory. It had similar lesson content as the control group but had different learning objectives and assessments anchored on Moore's constructs of structure, dialogue, and autonomy. Also, the learning objectives and assessments of the modules for the experimental group focused on civic literacy and were designed according to the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains.

Lesson Plans. The researcher created six (6) lesson plans for teaching the topics of UCSP for the final term. One lesson plan was created and utilized per topic. There were two types of lesson plans that were utilized in the study: (1) the typical or traditional lesson plan for the control group. It comprised the following elements: a. objectives, b. Subject Matter, c. Procedure – c.1 Preliminary Activities, c.2 Motivation, c.3 Discussion, and c.4. Activities, d. Assessment, and e. Assignment, and (2) a lesson plan anchored on Moore's theory and focused more on the civic literacy of students. The Transactional Distance Learning approach, specifically the structure, dialogue, and autonomy were considered in drafting the lesson plan's content, especially in the discussion, activities, assessment, and assignment to ensure that the approach was utilized in every lesson. In writing the lesson plan, the researcher showed the 3 constructs (structure, dialogue, and autonomy) in the content. The first construct was structure and it was integrated into the teaching approach by including learning materials that could lessen the transactional distance such as improvised modules, Mentimeter, Padlet, and other learning materials that would promote class interaction and independent learning. The second construct was dialogue and it was integrated into the activities and assessments to promote active class participation or interaction through debate, panel discussion, think-pair-share, buzz session, brainstorming, and Socratic Method. The third construct was the autonomy of promoting independent learning during the asynchronous period. This construct relied on the 'structure construct' because the more structured the learning materials are, the more independent the students could be, so the researcher assured the use of highly structured materials in the class during the asynchronous period. All in all, the lesson plan served as the teacher's guide to warrant

the implementation of the Transactional Distance Learning approach in the experimental group, specifically the structure, dialogue, and autonomy.

Pre-test and Post-test. The researcher created a 50-item pretest and post-test reviewed by validators. The appropriateness of language was checked by the grammarian while the accuracy of content was examined by the social science and research teachers before it was submitted for ethics review. Questions were framed on Bloom's Taxonomy particularly on the comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation since it intended to test the civic literacy of students.

Validation of Instruments

The validation of the research instruments is as follows:

Course Syllabus. The course syllabus did not undergo validation because it was a departmental syllabus already prepared by the UCSP teachers before the 1st semester started and it was already approved by the Social Science subject coordinator and Academic Head of the High School Department of the University of Makati.

Learning Modules. The learning modules underwent validation of content through an expert-driven validation. The researcher requested 3 field experts to scrutinize the appropriateness of the content. The 3 field experts were Social Science professors (with MA or Ph.D. degree) from the University of Makati. Furthermore, the researcher selected evaluators that were certainly skilled in the aspects that they were tasked to examine.

Lesson Plan. In the same way, the lesson plans were validated by a language teacher and researcher's adviser to ensure accurate grammar and integration of Transactional Distance Learning in the teaching process.

Pre-test and Post-test. The researcher consulted experts (research and language teachers) to examine the accuracy of language and to ensure that the questions in the pre-test and post-test were equally distributed based on Bloom's comprehension, application, analysis, and evaluation.

Reliability

The instruments of the study, specifically the pre-test and post-test were subjected to a reliability test of internal consistency through the pilot test of 30 participants. The pilot test determined the stability of the instrument and the possible errors that may arise during the full-scale data collection. The data were analyzed using Cronbach's alpha to get its internal consistency. It is the commonly used measure when researchers wish to determine the internal consistency of a test (Laerd Statistics, 2018). The use of pilot testing is according to the broadly accurate principle which requires testing the questionnaire on at least 30 to 100 pilot participants before the full-scale administration of the instrument (SAGE, 2016) and if the same result is consistently achieved by using the same instrument under the same circumstances, the measurement is considered reliable (Laerd Statistics, 2018).

Administration

The researcher collected and secured the respondents' and parents' informed consent to participate in the test before the administration of the tests and the Transactional Distance

approach. The data collection was administered after the consent form from the respondents and the ethics review committee were settled. The pilot test, pre-test, and post-test were administered using Google Forms within 1 hour which was the standard number of hours to take a test in the research locale.

Retrieval

The generated data in the Google forms from the administered tests (pilot, pre-test, and post-test) were sorted and thoroughly analyzed by the researcher and statistician.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher wrote a letter of request to the Dean of the High School Department to conduct the study at the University of Makati. Also, consent of participation from the respondents was secured by the researcher before the conduct of the study. Before the execution of the transactional distance learning modality, the researcher made sure that the learning modules and lesson plans were already prepared and validated. There were two types of learning modules utilized in the study: (1) the standard learning modules of the University of Makati that were used by the control group, and (2) the modified learning modules that were used by the experimental group which focused on civic literacy. Additionally, lesson plans were categorized into two: (1) the traditional or typical lesson plan for the control group, and (2) a lesson plan that was anchored to the constructs of Moore's theory (dialogue, structure, and autonomy).

Due to the distance learning setup, the researcher used Google Forms to administer the test questionnaires to the respondents. The pretest was administered in the control and experimental group during the midterm period when there was still no treatment applied in the experimental

group. During the entire final term period, the Transactional Distance Learning modality was performed in the experimental group while the control group underwent the currently implemented UMaK distance learning modality. Post-test was administered after the final term period.

Statistical Treatments

This study utilized descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics is defined as quick descriptive coefficients that sum up a given data set which can be a representation of the entire or a sample of a population (Hayes, 2021) while inferential statistics draws conclusions from samples and generalizes them to the population (Singh, 2018). To ensure the accuracy of the statistical treatments used in this study, the researcher consulted a statistician for the evaluation of the appropriate statistical treatment. Particularly, the data were presented and analyzed through weighted mean, T-test, standard deviation, percentage, and learning gains. In this study, the weighted mean was used to present the average score of students in the pre-test and post-test. Conversely, a T-test for two sample means was used to determine if there is a significant difference in the variables within groups and between groups. Moreover, the T-test was used to test the hypothesis. Then, the standard deviation was used to compute the scores of the pre-test and post-test to identify the distribution of scores. Lastly, the learning gains determined the improvement of students' performance based on the results of the pre-test and post-test.

a. Weighted Mean - It is one of the measures of central tendency that takes into account the varying degrees of importance of the numbers in the data set by multiplying each number in the data set to a predetermined weight before the final calculation is made. The weighted mean was used to determine the weighted mean score of the experimental and control group in the civic literacy pre-test and post-test.

$$\bar{x}_w = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (w_i x_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n (w_i)}$$

b. T-test - A t-test is a type of inferential statistic used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups, which may be related to certain features. It was used to determine if there is a significant difference in the variables within groups and between groups.

$$t = \frac{m - \mu}{s/\sqrt{n}}$$

c. Standard Deviation - A standard deviation is a statistic that measures the dispersion of a dataset relative to its mean. The standard deviation was used to compare the data set of the experimental group and the control group concerning their weighted mean.

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma(x - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}}$$

Overall, the statistical formulas were enough to determine the efficacy of the Transactional Distance modality in the enhancement of the civic literacy of Grade 12 Senior High School Students of the University of Makati in their Understanding Culture, Society and Politics course.

Data Processing Analysis

This study used descriptive and inferential statistics to illustrate and analyze the data. It also utilized Excel as a research tool for processing and calculating data.

Weighted Mean. The weighted mean was computed to identify the average score of the data set of the experimental and control groups, wherein in the experimental group, the transactional distance approach was implemented while in the control group, the UMaK

distance learning was applied. The computation of the weighted mean also emphasized some data points from each group that contributed more “weight” than others.

T-test - The t-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the results of the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group in UCSP after the utilization of the transactional distance learning modality and it also determined if the modality enhanced the civic literacy of students in a particular group.

Standard Deviation. The standard deviation compared the civic literacy scores of students in each group (experimental and control group) and how dispersed the scores in each group concerning its weighted mean.

Furthermore, the researcher consulted a statistician to ensure the accurate sorting, computation, and display of data in the tables.

The table below was used to interpret the mean scores or data that were collected.

Table 1. Rating Scale for the Effectiveness of Transactional Distance Learning Modality in Enhancing the Civic Literacy of the Students.

A five-point rating scale using deciles was used to measure the effectiveness of the transactional distance learning modality in enhancing the civic literacy of students. The researcher’s statistician determined the statistical limit of the scale based on the 50-item test questionnaire of the study.

Table 1

NUMERICAL SCALE	STATISTICAL LIMIT	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
5	40.81 – 50.00	To a very great extent
4	30.61 – 40.80	To a great extent
3	20.41 – 30.60	To a small extent
2	10.21 – 20.40	To some extent
1	1.00 – 10.20	Not at all

Table 1 shows the five-point rating scale that was utilized in the study. The numerical scale above (1-5) represents the level of effectiveness of the transactional distance learning modality in enhancing the civic literacy of students with the following verbal description: 1- not at all, 2- to some extent, 3-to a small extent, 4-to a great extent, and 5-to a very great extent. The above scale has an equivalent statistical limit (1- lower limit; 50 upper limits) that is used to determine the efficacy of the intervention through the scores obtained by the students in the pre-test and post-test.

Table 2. Interpretation of T-value

SCALE	DECISION	DESCRIPTION
Computed t-value > tabular value	Reject Ho	There is a significant difference
Computed t-value < tabular value	Accept Ho	There is no significant difference

CHAPTER 3

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the collected data, the results of the performed statistical analysis, and the interpretation of the findings. These are presented in tabular form in the order of the respective research problems and it has the following headings: (1.) The level of civic literacy of the control group based on the results of the pre-test; (2.) The level of civic literacy of the experimental group based on the results of the pre-test; (3.) The difference between the pre-test level of civic literacy of the control and experimental groups; (4.) The level of civic literacy of the control group based on the results of the post-test; (5.) The level of civic literacy of the experimental group based on the results of the post-test; (6.) The difference between the post-test level of civic literacy of the control and experimental groups; (7.) The difference between the pre-test and post-test level of civic literacy of the control group; (8.) The difference between the pre-test and post-test level of civic literacy of the experimental group; and (9.) The learning gains of the control and experimental group based on the results of post-test.

Problem No. 1. The Level of Civic Literacy of the Control and Experimental Groups Based on the Results of the Pre-test

The control group which comprised 35 participants was given a 50-item civic literacy pre-test during the midterm period. The following shows the result of the pre-test.

Table 1

CONTROL GROUP	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	INTERPRETATION
Pre-test	29.14	6.39	To a small extent

As shown in Table 1 the result of the civic literacy pre-test of the control group has a mean score of 29.14 and a standard deviation of 6.39. It only means that the control group has performed to a **small extent** on their average score in the civic literacy pre-test and the standard deviation shows that the test scores of students are widely spread from the mean. Consequently, the result shows that students have a little knowledge in civic literacy which according to Best (2014) should be worked on by students because civic literacy plays a vital role in transforming students into socially engaged citizens.

Problem No. 2. The Level of Civic Literacy of the Experimental Group Based on the Results of the Pre-test

The experimental group which comprised 35 participants was given a 50-item civic literacy pre-test during the midterm period. The following shows the result of the pre-test.

Table 2

EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	INTERPRETATION
Pre-test	29.68	4.49	To a small extent

Table 2 shows the mean or average score of the students from the experimental group. It has a mean of 29.68 and a standard deviation of 4.49. This means that the experimental group has

performed to a small extent based on their average score in the civic literacy pre-test. The standard deviation shows that student's test scores are widely spread from the mean. These results indicate that students from the experimental group also have a small extent of civic literacy. It somehow proves Adarlo's (2017) statement that there is a challenge in educating the Filipino people to become critically aware of our society and that there should be a useful way of teaching that can bring on a critical approach to citizenship education.

Problem No. 3. The Difference Between the Pre-test Level of Civic Literacy of the Control and Experimental Groups

The control and experimental group both underwent a 50-item civic literacy pre-test and the mean score of each group was computed and compared to identify the significant difference between the two groups in terms of civic literacy. The table below shows the findings of the significant difference between the control group and the experimental group in terms of civic literacy with a 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3

GROUP	Mean	t-value	Sig-Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Control	29.14	-0.411	0.682	Accept	Not significant
Experimental	29.68				

Significance level: 0.05

In table 3 the control group obtained a mean score of 29.14 and the experimental group had 29.68 mean. On the other hand, the t-value between the two groups is -0.411 and its significant value is 0.682 with a significant level of 0.05. Using the scale for the interpretation of the t-value,

the result shows that there is no significant difference between the level of civic literacy of the control and experimental group. It may imply that the pre-test scores of the control group and experimental group are most likely on the same level. No group is superior based on their pre-test scores.

Problem No. 4. The Level of Civic Literacy of the Control Group Based on the Result of the Post-test

The control group which comprises 35 participants was given a 50-item civic literacy post-test after the final term. The following table shows the result of the post-test.

Table 4

CONTROL GROUP	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	INTERPRETATION
Post-test	28.43	8.49	To a small extent

Table 4 shows the result of the civic literacy post-test of the control group which has a mean score of 28.43 and a standard deviation of 8.49. It only means that the control group has performed to a **small extent** based on their average score in the civic literacy post-test and the standard deviation shows that the test scores of students are widely spread from the mean. The findings suggest that there is a need to enhance the strategies used in the control group to improve the civic literacy of students in distance learning. One of the proposed approaches is the application of Moore’s Theory in distance learning. According to Abuhassna and Yahaya (2018), who also studied distance learning through an interventional online module based on Moore’s transactional distance theory, the said approach is effective in the education and learning system in terms of

comprehension, remembering, and some of the processes required in the methodical stages of education.

Problem No. 5. The Level of Civic Literacy of the Experimental Group Based on the Result of the Post-test

The experimental group which comprised 35 participants was given a 50-item civic literacy post-test after the final term. The following table shows the result of the post-test.

Table 5

CONTROL GROUP	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	INTERPRETATION
Post-test	33.51	4.90	To a great extent

Table 5 presents the result of the civic literacy post-test of the experimental group after the application of the transactional distance learning modality that the researcher has administered as an intervention to the group. The table shows the 33.51 mean scores of the experimental group and a standard deviation of 4.90. This means that the experimental group has performed to a **great extent** based on their average score in the civic literacy post-test and the standard deviation shows that the test scores of students are widely spread from the mean.

Consequently, the post-test of the experimental group implies that the students improved their civic literacy after the intervention. Nonetheless, the findings of Abuhassna and Yahaya (2018), who studied students' utilization of distance learning through an interventional online module based on Moore's transactional distance theory, stated on the results of their study that students under the intervention had a good result in the achievement test. However, it has the same

result as the control group. On the other hand, Gary Falloon's results of his study both show the positive and negative impacts of distance learning. He used Moore's concepts of Transactional Distance in examining the efficacy of using the virtual classroom to promote quality dialogue and explored how both internal and external structural elements related to the purpose and use of the classroom affected the learner's sense of autonomy. According to him, there is a complexity of the relationship that exists between the elements of Moore's theory, and how the implementation of an external structuring technology such as the virtual classroom, can have both positive impacts (dialogue creation) and negative impacts (diminished sense of learner autonomy). The findings of the study stated the following: (a) the use of a virtual classroom can add up to the enhancement of quality dialogue. However, it can be considered a double-edged sword, in a way that it has a positive effect on structural aspects and a negative effect on students' autonomy; (b) because of the nature of synchronous class in a virtual classroom, it affects the students in engaging a purposeful dialogue. There are participants of the study who stated that they felt hesitant to participate for the reason that the environment in a virtual classroom does not have enough time to generate their comments or input and they do not want to run the risk of "looking silly" in front of their peers; (c) the theory of Moore needs for a workable balance to be struck between students' autonomy and course structure so that the students could maintain a sense of empowerment and ownership of the learning, also, the structure of the course must provide enough direction and the standards and expectations of performance should be clearly communicated; and (d) the last factor that affects the participant's ability to engage in dialogue is the impact of technical and infrastructural issues such as the quality of broadband, computer equipment of adequate specification, and the students' level of technical competence. Overall, the study provided an important measure of the efficacy of using the virtual classroom to enhance quality dialogue, while

at the same time identifying areas where the theory may need reconsidering in light of the arrival of digital technologies and online learning to the distance learning landscape.

Problem No. 6. The Significant Difference Between the Level of Civic Literacy of the Control and Experimental Groups Based on the Result of the Post-test

The control and experimental group both undergo a 50-item civic literacy post-test to identify the difference between the civic literacy of the two groups. The table below shows the findings of the data that has been collected.

Table 6

GROUP	MEAN	t-value	Sig-Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Control	28.43	-3.068	0.003	Reject	Significant
Experimental	33.51				

Significance level: 0.05

In table 6 the control group obtained a mean score of 28.43 and the experimental group acquired 33.51 mean. On the other hand, the t-value between the two groups is -3.068, its significant value is 0.003, and it has a significant level of 0.05. Using the scale for the interpretation of the t-value, the results show that there is a significant difference between the level of civic literacy of the control and experimental group. It implies that the post-test scores of the control group and experimental group are not on the same level. The experimental group is most likely superior to the control group in terms of the post-test scores. Meaning, that the experimental group became more civic literate than the control group. The result differs from the study of Abuhassna

and Yahaya (2018) where they observed that there is no significant difference in mean scores for remembering, understanding, or application between the control and intervention groups before and after the intervention. Overall, their study found no statistically significant differences between groups in the majority of study domains, including student satisfaction, interaction and collaboration, and learning autonomy. That's why according to Abuhassna and Yahaya the results of their study come up with evidence that the distance education approach is effective in the education and learning system in terms of comprehension, remembering, and some of the processes required in the methodical stages of education because there were no substantial differences within and between the two methods (online and face-to-face).

Problem No. 7. The Significant Difference Between the Results of the Pre-test and Post-test of the Control Group in UCSP after the Utilization of the Non-Transactional Distance Learning Modality

The control group of 35 students underwent non-transactional distance learning in the subject UCSP. This group was given a 50-item civic literacy pre-test and post-test. The table below shows the difference between the results of their civic literacy pre-test and post-test.

Table 7

TEST	Mean	t-value	Sig-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Pre-test	29.14	0.463	0.646	Accept	Not Significant
Post-test	28.43				

Table 7 shows the mean score of the control group in the pre-test which is 29.14 and 28.43 mean score in the post-test with a t-value of 0.463. The significance value is 0.646. The mean difference and sig-value on this table indicate that there is little difference between the control group's civic literacy pre-test and post-test results. Therefore, it denotes that there is no significant difference between the results of the pre-test and post-test of the control group in UCSP after the utilization of the non-transactional distance learning modality. Meaning, that the students under the control group have the same civic literacy level before and after taking the UCSP subject under the non-transactional distance learning modality. The same result could be observed in the study of Abuhassna and Yahaya (2018) about the utilization of distance learning through an interventional online module based on Moore's transactional distance theory, in the former study, the students under the control group who did not receive intended intervention in the experimental research had no significant difference in mean scores for remembering, understanding or application.

Problem No. 8. The Significant Difference Between the Results of the Pre-test and Post-test of the Experimental Group in UCSP after the Utilization of the Transactional Distance Learning Modality

The experimental group which comprised 35 students underwent transactional distance learning in the subject UCSP. This group was given a 50-item civic literacy pre-test and post-test. The table below shows the difference between the results of the civic literacy of the experimental group in the pre-test and post-test.

Table 8

TEST	Mean	t-value	Sig-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Pre-test	29.68	-3.656	0.001	Reject	Significant
Post-test	33.51				

Table 8 shows the mean score of the experimental group in the pre-test which is 29.68 and 33.51 mean score in the post-test with a t-value of -3.656. The significance value is 0.001. The mean difference and sig-value on this table indicate that there is a difference between the experimental group's civic literacy pre-test and post-test results. Therefore, it denotes that there is a significant difference between the results of the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group in UCSP after the utilization of the transactional distance learning modality. Meaning, that the students in the experimental group have improved their civic literacy level after taking the UCSP subject under the transactional distance learning modality. The findings suggest that the use of Moore's Theory in teaching UCSP, considering the structure, dialogue, and autonomy in the teaching-learning process could help improve the civic literacy of students in distance learning. On the other hand, the study of Abuhassna and Yahaya (2018), which is limited to the structure and only employed an interventional online module based on Moore's transactional distance theory in distance learning, found that there was no significant difference in the mean scores for students' collaboration and interaction, satisfaction, and learning autonomy within the intervention group before and after the intervention. However, the present study utilized different strategies and activities that strengthen the structure, dialogue, and autonomy in distance learning which was found effective in improving the civic literacy of students.

Problem No. 9. The Learning Gains of the Control and Experimental Group Based on the Results of Pre-test and Pos-test

The control and experimental group which comprised 35 students each underwent transactional distance learning in the subject UCSP. This group has given a 50-item civic literacy pre-test and post-test. The following tables show the learning gains of students from the two groups based on the results of their civic literacy pre-test and post-test.

Table 9

Learning Gains Test Calculation Results			
Student	Experimental Group	Student	Control Group
	N-Gain Score (%)		N-Gain Score (%)
1	13.33	1	-68.18
2	-17.65	2	27.27
3	41.18	3	27.27
4	31.58	4	-41.67
5	36.36	5	-12.5
6	32	6	-150
7	8	7	-52.38
8	-17.65	8	11.76
9	52.94	9	-81.82
10	9.09	10	0
11	-80	11	34.48
12	23.53	12	4.17
13	17.39	13	14.29
14	81.82	14	-44.44
15	61.54	15	3.85
16	-38.89	16	12
17	26.09	17	-44.44
18	41.18	18	56.25
19	12.5	19	59.09
20	5.88	20	-12.5
21	21.43	21	-64.71
22	6.25	22	-24
23	22.73	23	52.17
24	9.52	24	20
25	33.33	25	41.67
26	9.09	26	14.71
27	38.1	27	-285.71
28	33.33	28	6.25
29	41.67	29	58.33
30	-5	30	35
31	-11.76	31	-52.63
32	21.05	32	2.56
33	30	33	0
34	-22.22	34	36.36
35	-14.29	35	-57.89
Mean	15.81	Mean	-13.58
Minimum	-80.00	Minimum	-285.75
Maximum	81.82	Maximum	59.09

Note: $G > 0.7$ = High; $0.3 \leq G \leq 0.7$ = Average; $G < 0.3$ = Low (Meltzer, 2008)

Table 9 presents the learning gains obtained by the 35 students both from the control and experimental group. The first two columns are the learning gains of the class from the experimental group. It has an average learning gain of 15.81, a minimum of -80.00, and a maximum of 81.82. This means that: out of 35 students from the experimental group, the majority or average learning gain obtained is 15.81; the minimum or lowest learning gain by the class is -80.00 and the maximum or highest learning gain by the class is 81.82.

On the other hand, the last two columns of the table present the learning gains of the class from the control group. It has a mean or average learning gain of -13.58, a minimum of -285.75, and a maximum of 59.09. This means that: out of 35 students from the control group, the majority or average learning gain obtained is -13.58; the minimum or lowest learning gain by the class is -285.75 and the maximum or highest learning gain by the class is 59.09.

Table 10

Group	Learning Gain Average	Interpretation
Experimental	15.81	Low Learning Gain
Control	-13.58	Low Learning Gain

Note: $G > 0.7 = \text{High}$; $0.3 \leq G \leq 0.7 = \text{Average}$; $G < 0.3 = \text{Low}$ (Meltzer, 2008)

Table 10 shows the learning gain obtained by the control and experimental group based on the results of the pre-test and post-test. The overall learning gain acquired by the experimental group is 15.81 while the control group is -13.58. The learning gains by these two groups both fall under the interpretation of "low learning gain" based on Meltzer's guide.

However, there is a big difference between the learning gains of these two groups. The experimental group is far higher than the control group for it acquires a 15.81 (a positive value) than the control for it gets -13.58 (a negative value). Overall, the experimental group still had little improvement after the intervention or after the utilization of transactional distance learning has been made.

Overall, the utilization of distance learning modality could be a basis for creating a transactional distance learning model in UCSP for it would result in effective learning of students. This is somehow supported by the ideas and conclusions of Abuhassna and Yahaya in their study. They have posited that distance education modality is effective in the education and learning system in terms of the following: understanding, remembering, and some of the processes required in the systematic stages of education. It also disclosed that there were no substantial differences within and between the two methods (online and face-to-face), which means that students in online courses exhibit good results in conjunction with face-to-face groups.

CHAPTER 4
SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND
RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings and conclusions obtained from the conduct of the study which is to determine the effectiveness of the Transactional Distance Learning modality in enhancing the civic literacy of Grade 12 senior high school students of the University of Makati in the subject Understanding Culture, Society and Politics (UCSP). It also provides recommendations that can be pursued by social science teachers and other stakeholders in education.

The study was conducted at the Higher School of the University of Makati in the 1st Semester of the School Year 2021-2022. The respondents of the study are Grade 12 senior high school students who took up the subject Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics. It applied quantitative research design and experimental methods; specifically, the randomized or true experiment. Relevant data were obtained through pre-test and post-test. The statistical tools that were used are weighted mean, T-test, standard deviation, and learning gain.

Summary and Conclusions

The data collected in the study established the following major findings: *1) grade 12 students from the control group have the same level of civic literacy before and after taking the subject UCSP using the UMAK distance learning modality.* This is evident in the data collected from the pre-test with a mean score of 29.14 and post-test results with a mean score of 28.43, with a t-value of 0.463. Therefore, it denotes that there is no significant difference between the results

of the pre-test and post-test of the control group in the UCSP subject. The result implies that students in the control group have learned to a small extent under UMAK distance learning. The students in the control group did not undergo any intervention, instead, the usual distance learning modality in the University of Makati High School Department was utilized in the control group. This includes four times a month of synchronous classes wherein the teacher taught the students through google meet with PowerPoint as instructional material. Moreover, civic literacy is also incorporated into the activities during the synchronous meeting. Aside from synchronous classes, there were also asynchronous classes (four times a month) in which students can do self-paced learning using the UCSP modules. The students answer the activity in learning modules according to the scheduled topic for each week. There might be factors of why the control group has learned to a small extent after taking the UCSP subject, these factors may include the usual instructional learning setup, the limited synchronous meeting, and the design of instructional materials. It is important to consider sufficient dialogue in the distance learning class and to ensure that the structure of the module encourages self-paced learning. The claims are supported by the idea of Simonson et al. (2019), according to them, interactive communication, connecting the students, resources, and teachers is one of the major elements of distance learning. Interactive communication is vital in the distance learning setup. That's why teachers and students should have good communication and interaction be it during synchronous or asynchronous classes. It is also essential that students have the means to interact with one another through the help of various resources such as electronic media and most importantly with the teacher's guidance. Also, it was reiterated that the teachers should ensure interaction with the students and must guarantee that the resources used would encourage learning. Aside from the aforementioned factors, there might be extraneous variables or challenges that may affect the performance of the control group in the

distance learning setup. It was mentioned in the study of Aguilar and Torres (2021) that there were four self-perceived challenges in online learning and these are technological and infrastructural difficulties, individual readiness, instructional struggles, and domestic barriers. That is why it is suggested that there is a need for re-evaluation and modification of current online learning to address the issues in distance learning and develop an authentic model for technology-driven and care-center education. The second major finding of this study is that 2) *Transactional Distance Learning is effective in the enhancement of civic literacy of students in the experimental group*. Based on the data collected, students in the experimental group gained a great extent of civic literacy after the intervention. Post-test results showed that the experimental group got 33.51 mean scores and a standard deviation of 4.90 which is interpreted as 'to a great extent'. Moreover, the data showed that there is a significant difference between the results of the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group wherein the civic literacy of students improved from 'small extent' to 'great extent' after the utilization of the transactional distance learning modality. In comparison to the post-test results of the control group, it is very evident that the experimental group is superior in terms of the post-test scores. Based on the results, the researcher may conclude that the application of Moore's Transactional Distance Theory could improve civic literacy of students especially when the structure, dialogue, and autonomy in the distance learning setup are sufficient. Accordingly, the following are some possible reasons why the students in the experimental group gained a great extent of civic literacy after the intervention: (1.) First factor. The utilization of transactional distance learning anchored on Moore's theory helped improve the students. The integration of the three constructs of his theory namely dialogue, structure, and autonomy in the UCSP instructional materials such as lesson plans and learning modules affected the students' learning. The *construct of dialogue* is when teachers and learners interact with one another; like

when the teacher gives instruction and the student responds, in such a manner, a dialogue is developed (Moore, 1997). The main goal of the dialogue is to improve the understanding of the student in a teaching-learning relationship. Moore posited that this is the most essential part of the relationship of student and teacher for it requires interaction with expected qualities in the level of conversation such as both parties should be actively participating, dialogue should be meaningful, encouraging, have the willingness to listen and share thoughts, and lastly, both of them must be appreciative. In this study, dialogue was highly incorporated into the lesson plans and learning modules to encourage students to become more participative and to listen attentively in class discussions. The learning strategies were also designed to enrich dialogue during synchronous classes. These strategies are *debate*, *panel discussion*, *think-pair-share*, *buzz sessions*, *brainstorming*, and *the Socratic method*. Hence, all of these strategies encouraged the students to engage in meaningful dialogue; (2.) Second factor. *The construct of structure* which determines the transactional distance in the teaching-learning process. Structure refers to the elements in the course design or how the teaching program is structured so that it can be delivered through different communications media (Moore, 1997). A minimally structured course or program can lessen the transactional distance if it is designed properly based on the needs of the students and the contents must still require interactions, also, it should not be pre-determined according to Moore. The medium used in delivering the lesson is also a factor. For instance, using technology like computers and self-study printed materials with properly structured content will likely minimize the transactional distance for it promotes more interactive dialogue between students and teachers. In the conducted study, the concept of “structure” was applied by teaching the UCSP subject in which the program or flow of the lesson plan in every learning session is structured to encourage dialogue (synchronous) and self-paced learning (asynchronous). Thus, the structure creates sufficient

dialogue (synchronous) and autonomy (asynchronous) and lessens the transactional distance. The structured activities that have been utilized during learning sessions are *graphic organizer, module, Mentimeter, Padlet, Facebook group page, and improvised modules*; (3.) Third factor. The learner's *autonomy*. Moore (1997) described autonomy as the extent to which the learner exerts control over learning procedures. It tells about the individual responsibility of the students in the learning process. Giving judgments and taking decisions about strategies for studying are some of the duties the students must possess in a distance education setup. In the study, autonomy was observed in the students during asynchronous learning wherein each of them independently completed the following tasks/activities: *learning diaries, concept maps, reflective writing, creating digital newspapers, diagram analysis, and creating FAQ flyers*. These activities allow the students to use their own strategies which encourage them to do self-paced learning. This strategy may help break the transactional distance and enhance the student's learning. Hence, it seems that all of the constructs (dialogue, structure, autonomy) from Moore's Theory were effective in enhancing the learning of students, specifically the civic literacy of students. Similarly, Falloon (2011), who also used Moore's concepts of Transactional Distance in examining the efficacy of using the virtual classroom to promote quality dialogue, identified that the use of a virtual classroom can add up to the enhancement of quality dialogue between students and teachers. However, it can be considered a double-edged sword, in a way that it has a positive effect on structural aspects and a negative effect on students' autonomy; because of the nature of synchronous class in a virtual classroom, it affects the students in engaging a purposeful dialogue. There are participants of the study who stated that they felt hesitant to participate for the reason that the environment in a virtual classroom does not have enough time to generate their comments or input and they do not want to run the risk of "looking silly" in front of their peers. Conversely,

the present study considers the adequacy of structure, dialogue, and autonomy in the distance learning setup which positively affects the civic literacy of students. Hence, the application of Moore's transactional distance constructs such as dialogue, structure, and autonomy may have different effects if it will be applied to various teaching-learning setups and levels of students. In this study, the constructs of Moore's Theory were applied in teaching UCSP subject to the Grade 12 students in a distance learning modality.

Lastly, the third major finding of this study is that *the transactional distance learning modality is effective*. It can be observed in the gathered data based on the pre-test and post-test of the control and experimental group. However, when it comes to the learning gains, the experimental group got an interpretation of low learning gain based on Meltzer's guide. The overall learning gain acquired by the experimental group is 15.81 while the control group is -13.58. The learning gains by these two groups both fall under the interpretation of "low learning gain" based on Meltzer's guide. Nevertheless, there is a big difference between the learning gains of these two groups. The experimental group is far higher than the control group for it acquires a 15.81 (a positive value) than the control for it gets -13.58 (a negative value). Overall, the experimental group still had little improvement after the intervention or after the utilization of transactional distance learning was made.

To conclude, it needs further studies to prove the effectiveness of transactional distance learning modality. A much longer time to conduct the study and add more activities and strategies (anchored on Moore's theory) is highly recommended.

The Transactional Distance Learning Model to Help Improve the Civic Literacy of Students in UCSP Course

The following transactional distance learning model in teaching UCSP course is proposed to help improve students' civic literacy. The model comprises the ideal teaching instructions that can be used in a distance learning environment.

Figure 1. UCSP Transactional Distance Learning Model

Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics subject has learning competencies that the students must acquire at the end of the course. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the Department of Education provided the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in all of the subjects offered in basic education for all schools in the country which served as a reference in identifying the learning approaches suitable to the local context and differences of learners (DM NO. 89, S. 2020). In this study, the researcher considered the MELCs in creating the civic literacy questionnaire for the learning needs assessments of the students. Before the intervention has been made, an assessment is needed to identify the level of civic literacy of UCSP students. By using this model, a teacher who will be using this assessment will not only determine the civic literacy needs of the students but also other learning needs that are based on the UCSP's most essential learning competencies.

After assessing the civic literacy needs of the UCSP students, the researcher started preparing the instructional materials needed for the intervention. The discussions, activities, and real-life situations examples of civic literacy must be incorporated into the instructional materials. The main constructs of Moore's theory (structure, dialogue, and autonomy) must be considered for it would help to break or lessen the transactional distance. It can be incorporated into instructional materials like in the lesson plans and learning modules. Enhancement of the structure, dialogue, and autonomy in the distance learning modality must be the ultimate support of the intervention.

The following constructs of Moore's theory can be specifically applied in the intervention:

Structure. Moore stated that this is a factor that determines the transactional distance in the teaching-learning process. Structure refers to the elements in the course design or how the teaching program is structured so that it can be delivered through different communications media (Moore,

1997). According to him, the program or course must be designed properly based on the needs of the students and the contents must still require interactions because it helps in breaking the transactional distance. In this study, the researcher had come up with highly structured inputs or activities such as a graphic organizer, module, Mentimeter, Padlet, FB group page, and improvised module.

Dialogue. According to Moore, the main goal of the dialogue is to improve the understanding of the student in a teaching-learning relationship. He also posited that this is the most essential part of the relationship of student and teacher for it requires interaction with expected qualities in the level of conversation such as both parties should be actively participating, dialogue should be meaningful, encouraging, has the willingness to listen and share thoughts, and lastly, both of them must be appreciative. Thus, in the actual execution of this construct the researcher integrated activities or learning strategies in which the students became more active and motivated to participate during synchronous learning. These activities are debate, panel discussion, think-pair-share, buzz session, brainstorming, and the Socratic method. Utilizing these strategies somehow helps the students to break the transactional distance.

Autonomy. Moore (1997) described autonomy as the extent to which the learner exerts control over learning procedures. It tells about the individual responsibility of the students in the learning process. Giving judgments and taking decisions about strategies for studying are some of the duties the students must possess in a distance education setup. In this study, the researcher incorporated learning tasks or activities for asynchronous classes in which the students work independently and complete their tasks using their own strategies. These activities are learning diaries, concept maps, reflective writing, creating digital newspapers, diagram analysis, and creating FAQ flyers.

Overall, the integration of civic literacy in teaching UCSP and the utilization of Moore's theory somehow helps to break and lessen transactional distance learning. The findings and analysis of data of this study proved that the students who have undergone transactional distance learning modality had improved their civic literacy. The learning strategies or activities that the researcher utilized may also be considered by teachers and future researchers who want to study more about transactional distance learning modality. Other learning activities and strategies may also be used provided that they will be applicable to Moore's theory (structure, dialogue, and autonomy). A longer period of intervention may be done to check if there will be significant changes in the effect of the intervention.

Recommendations

The study revealed that the Transactional Distance Learning modality enhanced the civic literacy of Grade 12 senior high school students of the University of Makati in the subject Understanding Culture, Society and Politics (UCSP). Hence, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. Since the effectiveness of the Transactional Distance Learning modality has been proven; teachers, specifically those who are teaching Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics, should consider using this modality, especially during this time wherein some schools are using blended learning (face-to-face and online setup). It would help them to achieve the specific learning objectives that they would like to impose in their lessons.

2. Educators must try to incorporate and execute the following: structure, dialogue, and autonomy in their lesson plan because it helps the students to become more active and independent in learning a specific topic or subject.
3. Transactional Distance Model should be considered in designing and creating UCSP Instructional materials such as modules and course syllabus.
4. The Department of Education must revisit the current curriculum guide of the UCSP course and consider incorporating the Transactional Distance Learning model to help improve future curricula suitable for all types of learning modalities.
5. Schools that are still imposing distance education, specifically online teaching, may consider utilizing the Transactional Distance Learning model to help their students achieve the desired learning outcomes for a specific course or subject.
6. Future researchers must conduct a similar study about the effectiveness of the Transactional Distance Learning model in a different course or subject, a larger number or group of students, and a longer time of observation and experimentation is recommended to determine if the same findings will be established.

